

1º filtro de seleção

Base: Pubmed

Total de artigos: 77

Artigos incluídos: 43 (CI1= 42, CI2= 1)

Artigos excluídos: 34 (CE1= 25, CE2= 0, CE3= 0, CE4= 0, CE5= 8, CE6= 1)

ID	Título	Link	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo da exclusão
001	A roadmap for implementation of patient-centered digital outcome measures in Parkinson's disease obtained using mobile health technologies	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30901495/	Obtaining reliable longitudinal information about everyday functioning from individuals with Parkinson's disease (PD) in natural environments is critical for clinical care and research. Despite advances in mobile health technologies, the implementation of digital outcome measures is hindered by a lack of consensus on the type and scope of measures, the most appropriate approach for data capture (eg, in clinic or at home), and the extraction of timely information that meets the needs of patients, clinicians, caregivers, and health care regulators. The Movement Disorder Society Task Force on Technology proposes the following objectives to facilitate the adoption of mobile health technologies: (1) identification of patient-centered and clinically relevant digital outcomes; (2) selection criteria for device combinations that offer an acceptable benefit-to-burden ratio to patients and that deliver reliable, clinically relevant insights; (3) development of an accessible, scalable, and secure platform for data integration and data analytics; and (4) agreement on a pathway for approval by regulators, adoption into e-health systems and implementation by health care organizations. We have developed a tentative roadmap that addresses these needs by providing the following deliverables: (1) results and interpretation of an online survey to define patient-relevant endpoints, (2) agreement on the selection criteria for use of device combinations, (3) an example of an open-source platform for integrating mobile health technology output, and (4) recommendations for assessing readiness for deployment of promising devices and algorithms suitable for regulatory approval. This concrete implementation guidance, harmonizing the collaborative endeavor among stakeholders, can improve assessments of individuals with PD, tailor symptomatic therapy, and enhance health care outcomes.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
002	Development and Implementation of the DHAPP Military eHealth Information Network System	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28521714/	Background: As the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS, the Global Fund, and the US President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief focus on reaching 90-90-90 goals, military health systems are scaling up to meet the data demands of these ambitious objectives. Methods: Since 2008, the US Department of Defense HIV/AIDS Prevention Program (DHAPP) has been working with military partners in 14 countries on implementation and adoption of a Military eHealth Information Network (MeHIN). Each country implementation plan followed a structured process using international eHealth standards. DHAPP worked with the private sector to develop a commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) electronic medical record (EMR) for the collection of data, including patient demographic information, clinical notes for general medical care, HIV encounters, voluntary medical male circumcision, and tuberculosis screening information. Results: The COTS software approach provided a zero-dollar software license and focused on sharing a single version of the EMR across countries, so that all countries could benefit from software enhancements and new features over time. DHAPP also worked with the public sector to modify open source disease surveillance		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			tools and open access of HIV training materials. Important lessons highlight challenges to eHealth implementation, including a paucity of technology infrastructure, military leadership rotations, and the need for basic computer skills building. Conclusion: While not simple, eHealth systems can be built and maintained with requisite security, flexibility, and reporting capabilities that provide critical information to improve the health of individuals and organizations.			
003	Leaf: an open-source, model-agnostic, data-driven web application for cohort discovery and translational biomedical research	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31592524/	Objective: Academic medical centers and health systems are increasingly challenged with supporting appropriate secondary use of clinical data. Enterprise data warehouses have emerged as central resources for these data, but often require an informatician to extract meaningful information, limiting direct access by end users. To overcome this challenge, we have developed Leaf, a lightweight self-service web application for querying clinical data from heterogeneous data models and sources. Materials and methods: Leaf utilizes a flexible biomedical concept system to define hierarchical concepts and ontologies. Each Leaf concept contains both textual representations and SQL query building blocks, exposed by a simple drag-and-drop user interface. Leaf generates abstract syntax trees which are compiled into dynamic SQL queries. Results: Leaf is a successful production-supported tool at the University of Washington, which hosts a central Leaf instance querying an enterprise data warehouse with over 300 active users. Through the support of UW Medicine (https://uwmedicine.org), the Institute of Translational Health Sciences (https://www.iths.org), and the National Center for Data to Health (https://ctsa.ncats.nih.gov/cd2h/), Leaf source code has been released into the public domain at https://github.com/uwrit/leaf . Discussion: Leaf allows the querying of single or multiple clinical databases simultaneously, even those of different data models. This enables fast installation without costly extraction or duplication. Conclusions: Leaf differs from existing cohort discovery tools because it does not specify a required data model and is designed to seamlessly leverage existing user authentication systems and clinical databases in situ. We believe Leaf to be useful for health system analytics, clinical research data warehouses, precision medicine biobanks, and clinical studies involving large patient cohorts.	CI1		
004	Extending an open-source tool to measure data quality: case report on Observational Health Data Science and Informatics (OHDSI)	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32229499/	Introduction: As the health system seeks to leverage large-scale data to inform population outcomes, the informatics community is developing tools for analysing these data. To support data quality assessment within such a tool, we extended the open-source software Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) to incorporate new functions useful for population health. Methods: We developed and tested methods to measure the completeness, timeliness and entropy of information. The new data quality methods were applied to over 100 million clinical messages received from emergency department information systems for use in public health syndromic surveillance systems. Discussion: While completeness and entropy methods were implemented by the OHDSI community, timeliness was not adopted as its context did not fit with the existing OHDSI domains. The case report examines the process and reasons for acceptance and rejection of ideas proposed to an open-source community like OHDSI.	CI1		

005	<p>Clinical Research Informatics: Contributions from 2018</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31419833/</p>	<p>Objectives: To summarize key contributions to current research in the field of Clinical Research Informatics (CRI) and to select best papers published in 2018. Method: A bibliographic search using a combination of MeSH descriptors and free-text terms on CRI was performed using PubMed, followed by a double-blind review in order to select a list of candidate best papers to be then peer-reviewed by external reviewers. After peer-review ranking, a consensus meeting of the editorial team was organized to conclude on the selection of best papers. Results: Among the 1,469 retrieved papers published in 2018 in the various areas of CRI, the full review process selected four best papers. The first best paper describes a simple algorithm detecting co-morbidities in Electronic Healthcare Records (EHRs) using a clinical data warehouse and a knowledge base. The authors of the second best paper present a federated algorithm for predicting heart failure hospital admissions based on patients' medical history described in their distributed EHRs. The third best paper reports the evaluation of an open source, interoperable, and scalable data quality assessment tool measuring completeness of data items, which can be run on different architectures (EHRs and Clinical Data Warehouses (CDWs) based on PCORnet or OMOP data models). The fourth best paper reports a data quality program conducted across 37 hospitals addressing data quality Issues through the whole data life cycle from patient to researcher. Conclusions: Research efforts in the CRI field currently focus on consolidating promises of early Distributed Research Networks aimed at maximizing the potential of large-scale, harmonized data from diverse, quickly developing digital sources. Data quality assessment methods and tools as well as privacy-enhancing techniques are major concerns. It is also notable that, following examples in the US and Asia, ambitious regional or national plans in Europe are launched that aim at developing big data and new artificial intelligence technologies to contribute to the understanding of health and diseases in whole populations and whole health systems, and returning actionable feedback loops to improve existing models of research and care. The use of "real-world" data is continuously increasing but the ultimate role of this data in clinical research remains to be determined.</p>	CE5	Revisão da literatura.
006	<p>The First, Comprehensive, Open-Source Culinary Medicine Curriculum for Health Professional Training Programs: A Global Reach</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33281516/</p>	<p>Providing a strong foundation in culinary medicine (CM)-including what constitutes a healthy diet and how to find, obtain, and prepare healthy and delicious food-is a cornerstone of educating health professionals to support patients in achieving better health outcomes. The Culinary Medicine Curriculum (CMC), published in collaboration with the American College of Lifestyle Medicine, is the first, comprehensive, open-source guide created to support the implementation of CM at health professional training programs (HPTPs) worldwide. The CMC is modeled after the successful CM elective course for Stanford University School of Medicine students. Key goals of the CMC include presenting healthy food as unapologetically delicious, quick, and inexpensive; translating lessons learned to healthy eating on-the-go; practicing motivational interviewing on healthy dietary behavior changes; and demonstrating how to launch a CM course. The CMC highlights a predominantly whole food, plant-based diet as seen through the lenses of different world flavors and culinary traditions. It was developed, published, and distributed with the aim of expanding CM by reducing barriers to creating CM courses</p>	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			<p>within most types of HPTPs and practice settings. During the first 2 months the CMC was available, it was downloaded 2379 times in 83 countries by a wide variety of health care professionals interested in teaching CM. The global interest in this first, freely available, evidence-based CMC underscores the demand for CM resources. Such resources could prove foundational in expediting development of CM courses and expanding the reach of CM and counseling on dietary behavior changes into patient care.</p>			
007	<p>Web Interactive Presentation of EPC Reports: A Foray Into Interactive Reports [Internet]</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31503436/</p>	<p>Background: Systematic reviews are consumed by different types of users to address an ever-expanding set of questions and needs. It is unlikely that a single static report will efficiently satisfy the diverse needs of diverse users. It might be practical and satisfactory to give users the ability to generate their own report from the information produced by the systematic review. Methods: We developed an open-source web-based interactive report presentation (IRP) of a systematic review on 14 nonsurgical treatments for Urinary Incontinence (UI) in women. We used data from a systematic review we conducted through the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality Evidence-based Practice Center Program for the Patient Centered Outcomes Research Institute. We presented wireframes (mockups) of the IRP to a panel of three Duke Health System stakeholders in teleconferences, and incorporated their feedback in the final IR, which includes a visual representation of the evidence base, and allows users to access generic or detailed descriptive and analytic information through a point-and-click interface. Subsequently, the stakeholders piloted the IRP and evaluated its ease of use by answering open ended questions. We proposed a roadmap for scalable IRPs of systematic reviews starting from a thematic analysis of these suggestions. Findings: The final tool (accessible at https://tol.infalliblekitty.com/#index) allows users to obtain descriptive and analytic results for a network of 14 treatment categories, various outcomes (cure, improvement, satisfaction, quality of life) and several subgroups (all women, older women, or those with stress or urge UI). Users can access descriptions overall or for specific sets of studies. The stakeholders were satisfied with the functionality of the tool, and commented on its ease of use. They proposed numerous augmentations, which we organized in themes of presentation (e.g., present information on numbers of trials on figures), analytic (e.g., allow on-the-fly subgroup analyses, explore tradeoffs between several outcomes) and information sharing (e.g., ability to import/export data from/to other software). A roadmap to satisfying these augmentations involves the following: (i) integrating analytic capabilities in the tool, (ii) incorporating ways to assess the tradeoffs between several distinct benefits and harms of interventions with minimal assumptions, (iii) defining an information technology standard for evidence synthesis objects (i.e., what information, in in what format, completely describes an evidence-base and its synthesis), and (iv) developing a rigorous representation of evidence synthesis objects as mathematical graphs that can be analyzed. Conclusions: In sum, we described a foray into an alternative view of a systematic review that complements a static systematic review report. Health system representatives found it useful and practical, and requested analytical, expository, and information sharing augmentations to the tool.</p>	CI2		

008	<p>The Role of Free/Libre and Open Source Software in Learning Health Systems</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28480476/</p>	<p>Objective: To give an overview of the role of Free/Libre and Open Source Software (FLOSS) in the context of secondary use of patient data to enable Learning Health Systems (LHSs). Methods: We conducted an environmental scan of the academic and grey literature utilising the MedFLOSS database of open source systems in healthcare to inform a discussion of the role of open source in developing LHSs that reuse patient data for research and quality improvement. Results: A wide range of FLOSS is identified that contributes to the information technology (IT) infrastructure of LHSs including operating systems, databases, frameworks, interoperability software, and mobile and web apps. The recent literature around the development and use of key clinical data management tools is also reviewed. Conclusions: FLOSS already plays a critical role in modern health IT infrastructure for the collection, storage, and analysis of patient data. The nature of FLOSS systems to be collaborative, modular, and modifiable may make open source approaches appropriate for building the digital infrastructure for a LHS.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
009	<p>EHDViz: clinical dashboard development using open-source technologies</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27013597/</p>	<p>Objective: To design, develop and prototype clinical dashboards to integrate high-frequency health and wellness data streams using interactive and real-time data visualisation and analytics modalities. Materials and methods: We developed a clinical dashboard development framework called electronic healthcare data visualization (EHDViz) toolkit for generating web-based, real-time clinical dashboards for visualising heterogeneous biomedical, healthcare and wellness data. The EHDViz is an extensible toolkit that uses R packages for data management, normalisation and producing high-quality visualisations over the web using R/Shiny web server architecture. We have developed use cases to illustrate utility of EHDViz in different scenarios of clinical and wellness setting as a visualisation aid for improving healthcare delivery. Results: Using EHDViz, we prototyped clinical dashboards to demonstrate the contextual versatility of EHDViz toolkit. An outpatient cohort was used to visualise population health management tasks (n=14,221), and an inpatient cohort was used to visualise real-time acuity risk in a clinical unit (n=445), and a quantified-self example using wellness data from a fitness activity monitor worn by a single individual was also discussed (n-of-1). The back-end system retrieves relevant data from data source, populates the main panel of the application and integrates user-defined data features in real-time and renders output using modern web browsers. The visualisation elements can be customised using health features, disease names, procedure names or medical codes to populate the visualisations. The source code of EHDViz and various prototypes developed using EHDViz are available in the public domain at http://ehdviz.dudleylab.org. Conclusions: Collaborative data visualisations, wellness trend predictions, risk estimation, proactive acuity status monitoring and knowledge of complex disease indicators are essential components of implementing data-driven precision medicine. As an open-source visualisation framework capable of integrating health assessment, EHDViz aims to be a valuable toolkit for rapid design, development and implementation of scalable clinical data visualisation dashboards.</p>	CII		
010	<p>Perspectives and</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33331825/</p>	<p>Background: Evidence-based health policy (EBHP) development is critical to the judicious use of public funds. EBHPs increase transparency, accountability, effectiveness, and efficiency of policies. Encouraging collaboration between researchers or</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de</p>

	<p>Experiences of Policy Makers, Researchers, Health Information Technology Professionals, and the Public on Evidence-Based Health Policies: Protocol for a Qualitative Study</p>		<p>knowledge producers and policy makers is important because both communities have distinct professional cultures, resulting in them working separately without understanding each other. Knowledge sharing is a complex process that requires understanding of cultural aspects that may reduce cultural differences and increase the use of common language. Health information technology (HIT) is a useful tool to increase knowledge translation, which may result in the transparent use of evidence and networking in developing EBHPs. Our vision is to leverage HIT tools for a better health system that includes digitalized, open source, evidence-based, and transparent ways for collaboration and development of robust mechanisms and for sharing of synthesized evidence with knowledge user-friendly forms. Objective: The aim of this study is to develop a conceptual framework on Knowledge translation and health Information Technology for Transparency (KhITT) in policy making and EBHPs (ie, the KhITT framework). The framework will be informed by the views of four key stakeholder groups (ie, policy makers, knowledge producers, HIT professionals, and the public) toward EBHP. The informants may also describe practices that demonstrate the EBHP development process and suggest technology platforms to enable this process. Methods: We propose an exploratory, descriptive qualitative study to take place in British Columbia, Canada, using in-depth semistructured interviews. To ensure data saturation and trustworthiness, we will use a nonprobability, purposive snowball sample of up to 15 eligible participants in each of the four stakeholder groups. We will analyze the data using content analysis. Results: The KhITT framework focuses on various stakeholders' perspectives to better understand their perceived needs and priorities in identifying issues with EBHP, in order to make informed recommendations. Ethics approval has been obtained by the harmonized Behavioural Research Ethics Board at the University of British Columbia. We anticipate that we will complete data collection and analysis by December 2020. Preliminary results will be published in summer 2021. Conclusions: Our ultimate goal of this study is to develop a conceptual framework and describe the technology platforms that would enable the EBHP process. We anticipate that our rigorous content analysis will be able to produce insights and themes that are able to address our objectives, contribute to an in-depth understanding of the EBHP process within British Columbia, highlight all influential factors, explicitly disseminate and communicate the study results, identify issues with EBHP and provide informed recommendations to address them, and enhance efforts toward transparent EBHPs.</p>			<p>um sistema.</p>
011	<p>A collaborative learning health system agent-based model: Computational and face validity</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34277939/</p>	<p>Introduction: Improving the healthcare system is a major public health challenge. Collaborative learning health systems (CLHS) - network organizations that allow all healthcare stakeholders to collaborate at scale - are a promising response. However, we know little about CLHS mechanisms of actions, nor how to optimize CLHS performance. Agent-based models (ABM) have been used to study a variety of complex systems. We translate the conceptual underpinnings of a CLHS to a computational model and demonstrate initial computational and face validity. Methods: CLHSs are organized to allow stakeholders (patients and families, clinicians, researchers) to collaborate, at scale, in the production and distribution of information, knowledge, and know-how for improvement. We build up a CLHS ABM from a population of</p>	C11		

			<p>patient- and doctor-agents, assign them characteristics, and set them into interaction, resulting in engagement, information, and knowledge to facilitate optimal treatment selection. To assess computational and face validity, we vary a single parameter - the degree to which patients influence other patients - and trace its effects on patient engagement, shared knowledge, and outcomes. Results: The CLHS ABM, developed in Python and using the open-source modeling framework Mesa, is delivered as a web application. The model is simulated on a cloud server and the user interface is a web browser using Python and Plotly Dash. Holding all other parameters steady, when patient influence increases, the overall patient population activation increases, leading to an increase in shared knowledge, and higher median patient outcomes. Conclusions: We present the first theoretically-derived computational model of CLHSs, demonstrating initial computational and face validity. These preliminary results suggest that modeling CLHSs using an ABM is feasible and potentially valid. A well-developed and validated computational model of the health system may have profound effects on understanding mechanisms of action, potential intervention targets, and ultimately translation to improved outcomes.</p>			
012	<p>Novel open-source electronic medical records system for palliative care in low-resource settings</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23941694/</p>	<p>Background: The need for palliative care in sub-Saharan Africa is staggering: this region shoulders over 67% of the global burden of HIV/AIDS and cancer. However, provisions for these essential services remain limited and poorly integrated with national health systems in most nations. Moreover, the evidence base for palliative care in the region remains scarce. This study chronicles the development and evaluation of DataPall, an open-source electronic medical records system that can be used to track patients, manage data, and generate reports for palliative care providers in these settings. DataPall was developed using design criteria encompassing both functional and technical objectives articulated by hospital leaders and palliative care staff at a leading palliative care center in Malawi. The database can be used with computers that run Windows XP SP 2 or newer, and does not require an internet connection for use. Subsequent to its development and implementation in two hospitals, DataPall was tested among both trained and untrained hospital staff populations on the basis of its usability with comparison to existing paper records systems as well as on the speed at which users could perform basic database functions. Additionally, all participants evaluated this program on a standard system usability scale. Results: In a study of health professionals in a Malawian hospital, DataPall enabled palliative care providers to find patients' appointments, on average, in less than half the time required to locate the same record in current paper records. Moreover, participants generated customizable reports documenting patient records and comprehensive reports on providers' activities with little training necessary. Participants affirmed this ease of use on the system usability scale. Conclusions: DataPall is a simple, effective electronic medical records system that can assist in developing an evidence base of clinical data for palliative care in low resource settings. The system is available at no cost, is specifically designed to chronicle care in the region, and is catered to meet the technical needs and user specifications of such facilities.</p>	CII		

013	<p>Strategies for more effective monitoring and evaluation systems in HIV programmatic scale-up in resource-limited settings: Implications for health systems strengthening</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19858942/</p>	<p>Program monitoring and evaluation (M&E) has the potential to be a cornerstone of health systems strengthening and of evidence-informed implementation and scale-up of HIV-related services in resource-limited settings. We discuss common challenges to M&E systems used in the rapid scale-up of HIV services as well as innovations that may have relevance to systems used to monitor, evaluate, and inform health systems strengthening. These include (1) Web-based applications with decentralized data entry and real-time access to summary reporting; (2) timely feedback of information to site and district staff; (3) site-level integration of traditionally siloed program area indicators; (4) longitudinal tracking of program and site characteristics; (5) geographic information systems; and (6) use of routinely collected aggregate data for epidemiologic analysis and operations research. Although conventionally used in the context of vertical programs, these approaches can form a foundation on which data relevant to other health services and systems can be layered, including prevention services, primary care, maternal-child health, and chronic disease management. Guiding principles for sustainable national M&E systems include country-led development and ownership, support for national programs and policies, interoperability, and employment of an open-source approach to software development.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
014	<p>Developing Open-Source Models for the US Health System: Practical Experiences and Challenges to Date with the Open-Source Value Project</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31392665/</p>	<p>The Innovation and Value Initiative started the Open-Source Value Project with the aim to improve the credibility and relevance of model-based value assessment in the context of the US healthcare environment. As a core activity of the Open-Source Value Project, the Innovation and Value Initiative develops and provides access to flexible open-source economic models that are developed iteratively based on public feedback and input. In this article, we describe our experience to date with the development of two currently released, Open-Source Value Project models, one in rheumatoid arthritis and one in epidermal growth factor receptor-positive non-small-cell lung cancer. We developed both Open-Source Value Project models using the statistical programming language R instead of spreadsheet software (i.e., Excel), which allows the models to capture multiple model structures, model sequential treatment with individual patient simulations, and improve integration with formal evidence synthesis. By developing the models in R, we were also able to use version control systems to manage changes to the source code, which is needed for iterative and collaborative model development. Similarly, Open-Source Value Project models are freely available to the public to provide maximum transparency and facilitate collaboration. Development of the rheumatoid arthritis and non-small-cell lung cancer model platforms has presented multiple challenges. The development of multiple components of the model platform tailored to different audiences, including web interfaces, required more resources than a cost-effectiveness analysis for a publication would. Furthermore, we faced methodological hurdles, in particular related to the incorporation of multiple competing model structures and novel elements of value. The iterative development based on public feedback also posed some challenges during the review phase, where methodological experts did not always understand feedback from clinicians and vice versa. Response to the Open-Source Value Project by the modeling community and patient organizations has been positive, but feedback from US decision makers has been limited to date. As we progress with this project, we hope to learn more about the feasibility, benefits, and challenges of an open-source and</p>	CII		

			collaborative approach to model development for value assessment.			
015	The International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer Early Lung Imaging Confederation	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32027538/	<p>Purpose: To improve outcomes for lung cancer through low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) early lung cancer detection. The International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer is developing the Early Lung Imaging Confederation (ELIC) to serve as an open-source, international, universally accessible environment to analyze large collections of quality-controlled LDCT images and associated biomedical data for research and routine screening care. Methods: ELIC is an international confederation that allows access to efficiently analyze large numbers of high-quality computed tomography (CT) images with associated de-identified clinical information without moving primary imaging/clinical or imaging data from its local or regional site of origin. Rather, ELIC uses a cloud-based infrastructure to distribute analysis tools to the local site of the stored imaging and clinical data, thereby allowing for research and quality studies to proceed in a vendor-neutral, collaborative environment. ELIC's hub-and-spoke architecture will be deployed to permit analysis of CT images and associated data in a secure environment, without any requirement to reveal the data itself (ie, privacy protecting). Identifiable data remain under local control, so the resulting environment complies with national regulations and mitigates against privacy or data disclosure risk. Results: The goal of pilot experiments is to connect image collections of LDCT scans that can be accurately analyzed in a fashion to support a global network using methodologies that can be readily scaled to accrued databases of sufficient size to develop and validate robust quantitative imaging tools. Conclusion: This initiative can rapidly accelerate improvements to the multidisciplinary management of early, curable lung cancer and other major thoracic diseases (eg, coronary artery disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) visualized on a screening LDCT scan. The addition of a facile, quantitative CT scanner image quality conformance process is a unique step toward improving the reliability of clinical decision support with CT screening worldwide.</p>	CI1		
016	Development and face validation of ultrasound-guided renal biopsy virtual trainer	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32038859/	<p>The overall prevalence of chronic kidney disease in the general population is ~14% with more than 661,000 Americans having a kidney failure. Ultrasound (US)-guided renal biopsy is a critically important tool in the evaluation and management of renal pathologies. This Letter presents KBVTrainer, a virtual simulator that the authors developed to train clinicians to improve procedural skill competence in US-guided renal biopsy. The simulator was built using low-cost hardware components and open source software libraries. They conducted a face validation study with five experts who were either adult/pediatric nephrologists or interventional/diagnostic radiologists. The trainer was rated very highly (>4.4) for the usefulness of the real US images (highest at 4.8), potential usefulness of the trainer in training for needle visualization, tracking, steadiness and hand-eye coordination, and overall promise of the trainer to be useful for training US-guided needle biopsies. The lowest score of 2.4 was received for the look and feel of the US probe and needle compared to clinical practice. The force feedback received a moderate score of 3.0. The clinical experts provided abundant verbal and written subjective feedback and were highly enthusiastic about using the trainer as a valuable tool for future trainees.</p>	CI1		

017	<p>Toward Strengthening Rehabilitation in Health Systems: Methods Used to Develop a WHO Package of Rehabilitation Interventions</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31207218/</p>	<p>Achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC) is a World Health Organization (WHO) strategic priority. UHC means "all people receive quality health services that meet their needs without being exposed to financial hardship in paying for the services." Rehabilitation is among the services included in UHC. As part of the WHO Rehabilitation 2030 call for action, WHO is developing its Package of Rehabilitation Interventions (PRI) to support ministries of health in planning, budgeting, and integrating rehabilitation interventions into health systems. The aim of this paper is to introduce and describe the PRI and its methodology. An advisory board composed of members from different WHO departments is overseeing the project, which is led by the WHO Rehabilitation Programme in collaboration with Cochrane Rehabilitation. The development of the PRI is conducted in 6 steps: (1) selection of health conditions (for which rehabilitation interventions will be included in the PRI) based on prevalences, related levels of disability, and expert opinion; (2) identification of rehabilitation interventions and related evidence for the selected health conditions from Clinical Practice Guidelines and Cochrane Reviews; (3) expert agreement on the inclusion of rehabilitation interventions in the PRI; (4) description of resources required for the provision of selected interventions; (5) peer review process, and (6) production of an open source web-based tool. Rehabilitation experts and consumers from all world regions will collaborate in the different steps. In developing the PRI, WHO is taking an important step toward strengthening rehabilitation in health systems, thus enabling more people to benefit from rehabilitation.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta uma estratégia da OMS que pode ser usada por governos no planejamento e integração de sistemas de saúde.</p>
018	<p>COVID-19 TestNorm: A tool to normalize COVID-19 testing names to LOINC codes</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32569358/</p>	<p>Large observational data networks that leverage routine clinical practice data in electronic health records (EHRs) are critical resources for research on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). Data normalization is a key challenge for the secondary use of EHRs for COVID-19 research across institutions. In this study, we addressed the challenge of automating the normalization of COVID-19 diagnostic tests, which are critical data elements, but for which controlled terminology terms were published after clinical implementation. We developed a simple but effective rule-based tool called COVID-19 TestNorm to automatically normalize local COVID-19 testing names to standard LOINC (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes) codes. COVID-19 TestNorm was developed and evaluated using 568 test names collected from 8 healthcare systems. Our results show that it could achieve an accuracy of 97.4% on an independent test set. COVID-19 TestNorm is available as an open-source package for developers and as an online Web application for end users (https://clamp.uth.edu/covid/loinc.php). We believe that it will be a useful tool to support secondary use of EHRs for research on COVID-19.</p>	CII	
019	<p>Evaluation and pilot implementation of essential interventions for the management of hypertension and prevention of</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32953086/</p>	<p>Background: Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are the leading cause of death worldwide and are a major burden in Tajikistan. The health system of Tajikistan is still shaped by the country's Soviet legacy and the pace of reform has been slow, with high patient out-of-pocket expenditure. The aim of this study is to determine the feasibility of implementing and evaluating essential interventions for the management of hypertension and prevention of cardiovascular disease in primary health care in Tajikistan. Methods and analysis: A pragmatic, sequential mixed methods explanatory design, composed of quantitative and qualitative strands will be used with greater weighting of the quantitative strand. A single geographic district was nominated by the Ministry</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>

	cardiovascular diseases in primary health care in the Republic of Tajikistan		of Health and chosen for implementation. All primary health care centres in the district that meet inclusion criteria will be included; half will be randomly assigned to the intervention arm and half to the control arm. The overall process is organized into seven steps: (1) refresh clinical decision-making tools including open source WHO PEN and HEARTS resources; (2) update training package for primary health care workers; (3) collection of baseline data; (4) training staff in intervention clinics; (5) implementation of protocols and implementation coaching; (6) collection of follow-up data after 12 months; (7) evaluation of results and sharing experience. Ethics and dissemination: Ethical review and approval have been obtained. Findings will be disseminated at the participant level, national level through a national conference of key stakeholders, and internationally through publication in an open-access peer review journal.			
020	Can ICTs contribute to the efficiency and provide equitable access to the health care system in Sub-Saharan Africa? The Mali experience	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21938322/	Objective: The aim of this study is to demonstrate from actual projects that ICT can contribute to the balance of health systems in developing countries and to equitable access to human resources and quality health care service. Our study is focused on two essential elements which are: i) Capacity building and support of health professionals, especially those in isolated areas using telemedicine tools; ii) Strengthening of hospital information systems by taking advantage of full potential offered by open-source software. Methods: Our research was performed on the activities carried out in Mali and in part through the RAFT (Réseau en Afrique Francophone pour la Télémédecine) Network. We focused mainly on the activities of e-learning, telemedicine, and hospital information systems. These include the use of platforms that work with low Internet connection bandwidth. With regard to information systems, our strategy is mainly focused on the improvement and implementation of open-source tools. Results: Several telemedicine application projects were reviewed including continuing online medical education and the support of isolated health professionals through the usage of innovative tools. This review covers the RAFT project for continuing medical education in French-speaking Africa, the tele-radiology project in Mali, the "EQUI-ResHuS" project for equal access to health over ICT in Mali, The "Pact-e.Santé" project for community health workers in Mali. We also detailed a large-scale experience of an open-source hospital information system implemented in Mali: "Cinz@n". Conclusion: We report on successful experiences in the field of telemedicine and on the evaluation by the end-users of the Cinz@n project, a pilot hospital information system in Mali. These reflect the potential of healthcare-ICT for Sub-Saharan African countries.		CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
021	Designing a medication timeline for patients and physicians	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30590550/	Objective: Most electronic health records display historical medication information only in a data table or clinician notes. We designed a medication timeline visualization intended to improve ease of use, speed, and accuracy in the ambulatory care of chronic disease. Materials and methods: We identified information needs for understanding a patient medication history, then applied human factors and interaction design principles to support that process. After research and analysis of existing medication lists and timelines to guide initial requirements, we hosted design workshops with multidisciplinary stakeholders to expand on our initial concepts. Subsequent core team meetings used an iterative user-centered design approach to refine our prototype. Finally, a		CI1	

			<p>small pilot evaluation of the design was conducted with practicing physicians. Results: We propose an open-source online prototype that incorporates user feedback from initial design workshops, and broad multidisciplinary audience feedback. We describe the applicable design principles associated with each of the prototype's key features. A pilot evaluation of the design showed improved physician performance in 5 common medication-related tasks, compared to tabular presentation of the same information. Discussion: There is industry interest in developing medication timelines based on the example prototype concepts. An open, standards-based technology platform could enable developers to create a medication timeline that could be deployable across any compatible health IT application. Conclusion: The design goal was to improve physician understanding of a patient's complex medication history, using a medication timeline visualization. Such a design could reduce temporal and cognitive load on physicians for improved and safer care.</p>			
022	<p>Towards the Application of Open Source Software in Developing National Electronic Health Record-Narrative Review Article</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26060634/</p>	<p>Electronic Health Record (EHR) is a repository of patient health information shared among multiple authorized users. As a modern method of storing and processing health information, it is a solution for improving quality, safety and efficiency of patient care and health system. However, establishment of EHR requires a significant investment of time and money. While many of healthcare providers have very limited capital, application of open source software would be considered as a solution in developing national electronic health record especially in countries with low income. The evidence showed that financial limitation is one of the obstacles to implement electronic health records in developing countries. Therefore, establishment of an open source EHR system capable of modifications according to the national requirements seems to be inevitable in Iran. The present study identifies the impact of application of open source software in developing national electronic health record in Iran.</p>		CE5	Revisão da literatura.
023	<p>Developing a representative community health survey sampling frame using open-source remote satellite imagery in Mozambique</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30373621/</p>	<p>Background: Lack of accurate data on the distribution of sub-national populations in low- and middle-income countries impairs planning, monitoring, and evaluation of interventions. Novel, low-cost methods to develop unbiased survey sampling frames at sub-national, sub-provincial, and even sub-district levels are urgently needed. This article details our experience using remote satellite imagery to develop a provincial-level representative community survey sampling frame to evaluate the effects of a 7-year health system intervention in Sofala Province, Mozambique. Methods: Mozambique's most recent census was conducted in 2007, and no data are readily available to generate enumeration areas for representative health survey sampling frames. To remedy this, we partnered with the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team to digitize every building in Sofala and Manica provinces (685,189 Sofala; 925,713 Manica) using up-to-date remote satellite imagery, with final results deposited in the open-source OpenStreetMap database. We then created a probability proportional to size sampling frame by overlaying a grid of 2.106 km resolution (0.02 decimal degrees) across each province, and calculating the number of buildings within each grid square. Squares containing buildings were used as our primary sampling unit with replacement. Study teams navigated to the geographic center of each selected square using geographic</p>		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			<p>positioning system coordinates, and then conducted a standard "random walk" procedure to select 20 households for each time a given square was selected. Based on sample size calculations, we targeted a minimum of 1500 households in each province. We selected 88 grids within each province to reach 1760 households, anticipating ongoing conflict and transport issues could preclude the inclusion of some clusters. Results: Civil conflict issues forced the exclusion of 8 of 31 subdistricts in Sofala and 15 of 39 subdistricts in Manica. Using Android tablets, Open Data Kit software, and a remote RedCap data capture system, our final sample included 1549 households in Sofala (4669 adults; 4766 children; 33 missing age) and 1538 households in Manica (4422 adults; 4898 children; 33 missing age). Conclusions: Other implementation or evaluation teams may consider employing similar methods to track population distributions for health systems planning or the development of representative sampling frames using remote satellite imagery</p>			
024	<p>MIRACUM: Medical Informatics in Research and Care in University Medicine</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30016814/</p>	<p>Introduction: This article is part of the Focus Theme of Methods of Information in Medicine on the German Medical Informatics Initiative. Similar to other large international data sharing networks (e.g. OHDSI, PCORnet, eMerge, RD-Connect) MIRACUM is a consortium of academic and hospital partners as well as one industrial partner in eight German cities which have joined forces to create interoperable data integration centres (DIC) and make data within those DIC available for innovative new IT solutions in patient care and medical research. Objectives: Sharing data shall be supported by common interoperable tools and services, in order to leverage the power of such data for biomedical discovery and moving towards a learning health system. This paper aims at illustrating the major building blocks and concepts which MIRACUM will apply to achieve this goal. Governance and policies: Besides establishing an efficient governance structure within the MIRACUM consortium (based on the steering board, a central administrative office, the general MIRACUM assembly, six working groups and the international scientific advisory board), defining DIC governance rules and data sharing policies, as well as establishing (at each MIRACUM DIC site, but also for MIRACUM in total) use and access committees are major building blocks for the success of such an endeavor. Architectural framework and methodology: The MIRACUM DIC architecture builds on a comprehensive ecosystem of reusable open source tools (MIRACOLIX), which are linkable and interoperable amongst each other, but also with the existing software environment of the MIRACUM hospitals. Efficient data protection measures, considering patient consent, data harmonization and a MIRACUM metadata repository as well as a common data model are major pillars of this framework. The methodological approach for shared data usage relies on a federated querying and analysis concept. Use cases: MIRACUM aims at proving the value of their DIC with three use cases: IT support for patient recruitment into clinical trials, the development and routine care implementation of a clinico-molecular predictive knowledge tool, and molecular-guided therapy recommendations in molecular tumor boards. Results: Based on the MIRACUM DIC release in the nine months conceptual phase first large scale analysis for stroke and colorectal cancer cohorts have been pursued. Discussion: Beyond all technological challenges successfully applying the MIRACUM tools for the enrichment of our knowledge about diagnostic and</p>	CII		

			therapeutic concepts, thus supporting the concept of a Learning Health System will be crucial for the acceptance and sustainability in the medical community and the MIRACUM university hospitals		
025	Cost and cost-effectiveness of point-of-care testing and treatment for sexually transmitted and genital infections in pregnancy in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic review protocol	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31727649/	Introduction: The economic and health burden of sexually transmitted and genital infections (henceforth, STIs) in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) is substantial. Left untreated, STIs during pregnancy may result in several adverse pregnancy and birth outcomes. Timely diagnosis and treatment at point-of-care (POC) can potentially improve these outcomes. Despite the availability and promotion of POC diagnostics for STIs as a key component of antenatal care in LMICs, their widespread use has been limited, owing to the high economic costs faced by individuals and health systems. To date, there have been no systematic reviews which explore the cost or cost-effectiveness of POC testing and treatment of STIs in pregnancy in LMICs. The objective of this protocol is to outline the methods that will compare, synthesise and appraise the existing literature in this domain. Methods and analysis: We will conduct literature searches in MEDLINE, Embase and Web of Science. To find additional literature, we will search Google Scholar and hand search reference lists of included papers. Two reviewers will independently search databases, screen titles, abstracts and full texts; when necessary a third reviewer will resolve disputes. Only cost and cost-effectiveness studies of POC testing and treatment of STIs, including syphilis, chlamydia, trichomonas, gonorrhoea and bacterial vaginosis, in pregnancy in LMICs will be included. Published checklists will be used to assess quality of reporting practices and methodological approaches. We will also assess risk of publication bias. Interstudy heterogeneity will be assessed and depending on variation between studies, a meta-analysis or narrative synthesis will be conducted. Ethics and dissemination: Ethical approval is not required as the review will use published literature. The results will be published in a peer-reviewed open source journal and presented at an international conference.	CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura.
026	BRIDG: a domain information model for translational and clinical protocol-driven research	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28339791/	Background: It is critical to integrate and analyze data from biological, translational, and clinical studies with data from health systems; however, electronic artifacts are stored in thousands of disparate systems that are often unable to readily exchange data. Objective: To facilitate meaningful data exchange, a model that presents a common understanding of biomedical research concepts and their relationships with health care semantics is required. The Biomedical Research Integrated Domain Group (BRIDG) domain information model fulfills this need. Software systems created from BRIDG have shared meaning "baked in," enabling interoperability among disparate systems. For nearly 10 years, the Clinical Data Standards Interchange Consortium, the National Cancer Institute, the US Food and Drug Administration, and Health Level 7 International have been key stakeholders in developing BRIDG. Methods: BRIDG is an open-source Unified Modeling Language-class model developed through use cases and harmonization with other models. Results: With its 4+ releases, BRIDG includes clinical and now translational research concepts in its Common, Protocol Representation, Study Conduct, Adverse Events, Regulatory, Statistical Analysis, Experiment, Biospecimen	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			and Molecular Biology subdomains. Interpretation: The model is a Clinical Data Standards Interchange Consortium, Health Level 7 International, and International Standards Organization standard that has been utilized in national and international standards-based software development projects. It will continue to mature and evolve in the areas of clinical imaging, pathology, ontology, and vocabulary support. BRIDG 4.1.1 and prior releases are freely available at https://bridgmodel.nci.nih.gov			
027	Evaluation of computerized health management information system for primary health care in rural India	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21078203/	Background: The Comprehensive Rural Health Services Project Ballabgarh, run by All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS), New Delhi has a computerized Health Management Information System (HMIS) since 1988. The HMIS at Ballabgarh has undergone evolution and is currently in its third version which uses generic and open source software. This study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of a computerized Health Management Information System in rural health system in India. Methods: The data for evaluation were collected by in-depth interviews of the stakeholders i.e. program managers (authors) and health workers. Health Workers from AIIMS and Non-AIIMS Primary Health Centers were interviewed to compare the manual with computerized HMIS. A cost comparison between the two methods was carried out based on market costs. The resource utilization for both manual and computerized HMIS was identified based on workers' interviews. Results: There have been no major hardware problems in use of computerized HMIS. More than 95% of data was found to be accurate. Health workers acknowledge the usefulness of HMIS in service delivery, data storage, generation of workplans and reports. For program managers, it provides a better tool for monitoring and supervision and data management. The initial cost incurred in computerization of two Primary Health Centers was estimated to be Indian National Rupee (INR) 1674,217 (USD 35,622). Equivalent annual incremental cost of capital items was estimated as INR 198,017 (USD 4213). The annual savings is around INR 894,283 (USD 11,924). Conclusion: The major advantage of computerization has been in saving of time of health workers in record keeping and report generation. The initial capital costs of computerization can be recovered within two years of implementation if the system is fully operational. Computerization has enabled implementation of a good system for service delivery, monitoring and supervision.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta uma avaliação.
028	MVSE: An R-package that estimates a climate-driven mosquito-borne viral suitability index	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32391139/	Viruses, such as dengue, Zika, yellow fever and chikungunya, depend on mosquitoes for transmission. Their epidemics typically present periodic patterns, linked to the underlying mosquito population dynamics, which are known to be driven by natural climate fluctuations. Understanding how climate dictates the timing and potential of viral transmission is essential for preparedness of public health systems and design of control strategies. While various alternative approaches have been proposed to estimate local transmission potential of such viruses, few open-source, ready to use and freely available software tools exist. We developed the Mosquito-borne Viral Suitability Estimator (MVSE) software package for the R programming environment. MVSE estimates the index P, a novel suitability index based on a climate-driven mathematical expression for the basic reproductive number of mosquito-borne viruses. By accounting for local humidity and temperature, as well as viral, vector and human priors, the index P can be estimated for specific	CI1		

			host and viral species in different regions of the globe. We describe the background theory, empirical support and biological interpretation of the index P. Using real-world examples spanning multiple epidemiological contexts, we further demonstrate MVSE's basic functionality, research and educational potentials.			
029	CovidCounties is an interactive real time tracker of the COVID19 pandemic at the level of US counties	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33199721/	Management of the COVID-19 pandemic has proven to be a significant challenge to policy makers. This is in large part due to uneven reporting and the absence of open-access visualization tools to present local trends and infer healthcare needs. Here we report the development of CovidCounties.org, an interactive web application that depicts daily disease trends at the level of US counties using time series plots and maps. This application is accompanied by a manually curated dataset that catalogs all major public policy actions made at the state-level, as well as technical validation of the primary data. Finally, the underlying code for the site is also provided as open source, enabling others to validate and learn from this work.	CI1		
030	Design and implementation of an affordable, public sector electronic medical record in rural Nepal	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28749321/	Introduction: Globally, electronic medical records are central to the infrastructure of modern healthcare systems. Yet the vast majority of electronic medical records have been designed for resource-rich environments and are not feasible in settings of poverty. Here we describe the design and implementation of an electronic medical record at a public sector district hospital in rural Nepal, and its subsequent expansion to an additional public sector facility. Development The electronic medical record was designed to solve for the following elements of public sector healthcare delivery: 1) integration of the systems across inpatient, surgical, outpatient, emergency, laboratory, radiology, and pharmacy sites of care; 2) effective data extraction for impact evaluation and government regulation; 3) optimization for longitudinal care provision and patient tracking; and 4) effectiveness for quality improvement initiatives. Application: For these purposes, we adapted Bahmni, a product built with open-source components for patient tracking, clinical protocols, pharmacy, laboratory, imaging, financial management, and supply logistics. In close partnership with government officials, we deployed the system in February of 2015, added on additional functionality, and iteratively improved the system over the following year. This experience enabled us then to deploy the system at an additional district-level hospital in a different part of the country in under four weeks. We discuss the implementation challenges and the strategies we pursued to build an electronic medical record for the public sector in rural Nepal. Discussion Over the course of 18 months, we were able to develop, deploy and iterate upon the electronic medical record, and then deploy the refined product at an additional facility within only four weeks. Our experience suggests the feasibility of an integrated electronic medical record for public sector care delivery even in settings of rural poverty.	CI1		
031	Implementation of an open-source robotic platform for SARS-CoV-2	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34260637/	The current global pandemic due to the SARS-CoV-2 has pushed the limits of global health systems across all aspects of clinical care, including laboratory diagnostics. Supply chain disruptions and rapidly-shifting markets have resulted in flash-scarcity of commercial laboratory reagents; this has motivated health care providers to search for alternative workflows to cope with the international increase in demand for SARS-CoV-2 testing. The aim of this study is to present a reproducible workflow for real time	CI1		

	testing by real-time RT-PCR		RT-PCR SARS-CoV-2 testing using OT-2 open-source liquid-handling robots (Opentrons, NY). We have developed a framework that includes a code template which is helpful for building different stand-alone robotic stations, capable of performing specific protocols. Such stations can be combined together to create a complex multi-stage workflow, from sample setup to real time RT-PCR. Using our open-source code, it is easy to create new stations or workflows from scratch, adapt existing templates to update the experimental protocols, or to fine-tune the code to fit specific needs. Using this framework, we developed the code for two different workflows and evaluated them using external quality assessment (EQA) samples from the European Molecular Genetics Quality Network (EMQN). The affordability of this platform makes automated SARS-CoV-2 PCR testing accessible for most laboratories and hospitals with qualified bioinformatics personnel. This platform also allows for flexibility, as it is not dependent on any specific commercial kit, and thus it can be quickly adapted to protocol changes, reagent, consumable shortages, or any other temporary material constraints.			
032	Addressing the unique healthcare needs of women: Opportunity for change exists at the intersection of precision health and learning health systems	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31245578/	Introduction: Women have unique healthcare needs that are not well addressed by our current healthcare system and with healthcare transformation underway the opportunity exists to avoid weaving these age-old problems into the fabric of the new healthcare design. myAva is an example of a learning health system integrated into a cloud-based precision health platform. The goal of myAva is to integrate the tools of precision health and principals of a learning health system to improve care for women, starting with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Methods: Putting patients at the center in designing a new style of healthcare has been an important concept underlying the development of myAva since inception. Understanding the needs of patients and providers is key to the development of myAva. Surveys were collected from members of the PCOS patient community and patient and medical advisory boards were recruited. For the pilot group comprehensive omic data, biometric and self-reported data were collected and integrated into a personalized health dashboard enabling providers to formulate personalized treatment plans. The ongoing collection of data will create continuous improvement of healthcare. Results: Precision health for chronic issues faced is in its infancy and although myriad challenges exist the potential to improve health outcomes is great. myAva's providers, patients, and advisors are encouraged by the early outcomes of the program with improved health outcomes and an increased sense of empowerment reported. It is clear that designing and implementing this type of care requires collaboration, the involvement of all stakeholders, with patients at the center		CEI	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
033	Pediatric-Collaborative Health Outcomes Information Registry (Peds-CHOIR): a learning health system to guide pediatric	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27280328/	The pediatric adaptation of the Collaborative Health Outcomes Information Registry (Peds-CHOIR) is a free, open-source, flexible learning health care system (LHS) that meets the call by the Institute of Medicine for the development of national registries to guide research and precision pain medicine. This report is a technical account of the first application of Peds-CHOIR with 3 aims: (1) to describe the design and implementation process of the LHS; (2) to highlight how the clinical system concurrently cultivates a research platform rich in breadth (eg, clinic characteristics) and depth (eg, unique patient- and caregiver-reporting patterns); and (3) to demonstrate the utility of capturing patient-caregiver dyad data in real time, with dynamic outcomes tracking that informs clinical decisions and delivery of	CI1		

	<p>pain research and treatment</p>		<p>treatments. Technical, financial, and systems-based considerations of Peds-CHOIR are discussed. Cross-sectional retrospective data from patients with chronic pain (N = 352; range, 8-17 years; mean, 13.9 years) and their caregivers are reported, including National Institutes of Health Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) domains (mobility, pain interference, fatigue, peer relations, anxiety, and depression) and the Pain Catastrophizing Scale. Consistent with the literature, analyses of initial visits revealed impairments across physical, psychological, and social domains. Patients and caregivers evidenced agreement in observable variables (mobility); however, caregivers consistently endorsed greater impairment regarding internal experiences (pain interference, fatigue, peer relations, anxiety, and depression) than patients' self-report. A platform like Peds-CHOIR highlights predictors of chronic pain outcomes on a group level and facilitates individually tailored treatment(s). Challenges of implementation and future directions are discussed.</p>			
<p>034</p>	<p>A resource management tool for public health continuity of operations during disasters</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24618165/</p>	<p>Objective: We developed and validated a user-centered information system to support the local planning of public health continuity of operations for the Community Health Services Division, Public Health - Seattle & King County, Washington. Methods: The Continuity of Operations Data Analysis (CODA) system was designed as a prototype developed using requirements identified through participatory design. CODA uses open-source software that links personnel contact and licensing information with needed skills and clinic locations for 821 employees at 14 public health clinics in Seattle and King County. Using a web-based interface, CODA can visualize locations of personnel in relationship to clinics to assist clinic managers in allocating public health personnel and resources under dynamic conditions. Results: Based on user input, the CODA prototype was designed as a low-cost, user-friendly system to inventory and manage public health resources. In emergency conditions, the system can run on a stand-alone battery-powered laptop computer. A formative evaluation by managers of multiple public health centers confirmed the prototype design's usefulness. Emergency management administrators also provided positive feedback about the system during a separate demonstration. Conclusions: Validation of the CODA information design prototype by public health managers and emergency management administrators demonstrates the potential usefulness of building a resource management system using open-source technologies and participatory design principles.</p>	<p>CII</p>		
<p>035</p>	<p>Electronic data collection and management system for global adult tobacco survey</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23569638/</p>	<p>Introduction: Portable handheld computers and electronic data management systems have been used for national surveys in many high-income countries, however their use in developing countries has been challenging due to varying geographical, economic, climatic, political and cultural environments. In order to monitor and measure global adult tobacco use, the World Health Organization and the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention initiated the Global Adult Tobacco Survey, a nationally representative household survey of adults, 15 years of age or older, using a standard core questionnaire, sample design, and data collection and management procedures. The Survey has been conducted in 14 low- and middle-income countries, using an electronic data collection and management system. This paper describes implementation of the electronic data collection system</p>		<p>CE5</p>	<p>Survey</p>

			and associated findings. Methods: The Survey was based on a comprehensive data management protocol, to enable standardized, globally comparable high quality data collection and management. It included adaptation to specific country needs, selection of appropriate handheld hardware devices, use of open source software, and building country capacity and provide technical support. Results: In its first phase, the Global Adult Tobacco Survey was successfully conducted between 2008 and 2010, using an electronic data collection and management system for interviews in 302,800 households in 14 countries. More than 2,644 handheld computers were fielded and over 2,634 fieldworkers, supervisors and monitors were trained to use them. Questionnaires were developed and programmed in 38 languages and scripts. The global hardware failure rate was < 1% and data loss was almost 0%. Conclusion: Electronic data collection and management systems can be used effectively for conducting nationally representative surveys, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, irrespective of geographical, climatic, political and cultural environments, and capacity-building at the country level is an important vehicle for Health System Strengthening.			
036	Design and development of a customizable telemedicine platform for improving access to healthcare for underserved populations	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29060446/	Telemedicine offers a method to bridge the healthcare access gap in low and middle income countries (LMICs) by connecting providers with patients using appropriate technology. Here we describe the design and development of a novel modular telemedicine platform, Intelhealth, that would enable health systems to connect remote doctors with patients in rural clinics using a customizable Android-based platform and a cloud-based electronic health record system at the backend (OpenMRS). This open source platform enables task shifting of medically relevant information gathering by a local health worker, transmission of this information to a remote doctor, and a telephonic conversation between the doctor and the patient that subsequently allows for delivery of an appropriate therapeutic plan. Intelhealth is designed to operate on a low bandwidth internet environment, and will be tested and validated in rural health clinics in India.	CE6	Duplicado (IEEE).	
037	Design of the Familial Hypercholesterolemia Australasia Network Registry: Creating Opportunities for Greater International Collaboration	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28344196/	Familial Hypercholesterolemia (FH) is the most common and serious monogenic disorder of lipoprotein metabolism that leads to premature coronary heart disease. There are over 65,000 people estimated to have FH in Australia, but many remain undiagnosed. Patients with FH are often under-treated, but with early detection, cascade family testing and adequate treatment, patient outcomes can improve. Patient registries are key tools for providing new information on FH and enhancing care worldwide. The development and design of the FH Australasia Network Registry is a crucial component in the comprehensive model of care for FH, which aims to provide a standardized, high-quality and cost-effective system of care that is likely to have the highest impact on patient outcomes. Informed by stakeholder engagement, the FH Australasia Network Registry was collaboratively developed by government, patient and clinical networks and research groups. The open-source, web-based Rare Disease Registry Framework was the architecture chosen for this registry owing to its open-source standards, modular design, interoperability, scalability and security features; all these are key components required to meet the ever changing clinical demands across regions. This paper provides a high level blueprint for other countries and jurisdictions to help inform and map out the critical features of an FH registry to meet their particular health system needs.	CI1		

038	<p>Query Health: standards-based, cross-platform population health surveillance</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24699371/</p>	<p>Objective: Understanding population-level health trends is essential to effectively monitor and improve public health. The Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology (ONC) Query Health initiative is a collaboration to develop a national architecture for distributed, population-level health queries across diverse clinical systems with disparate data models. Here we review Query Health activities, including a standards-based methodology, an open-source reference implementation, and three pilot projects. Materials and methods: Query Health defined a standards-based approach for distributed population health queries, using an ontology based on the Quality Data Model and Consolidated Clinical Document Architecture, Health Quality Measures Format (HQMF) as the query language, the Query Envelope as the secure transport layer, and the Quality Reporting Document Architecture as the result language. Results: We implemented this approach using Informatics for Integrating Biology and the Bedside (i2b2) and hQuery for data analytics and PopMedNet for access control, secure query distribution, and response. We deployed the reference implementation at three pilot sites: two public health departments (New York City and Massachusetts) and one pilot designed to support Food and Drug Administration post-market safety surveillance activities. The pilots were successful, although improved cross-platform data normalization is needed. Discussions: This initiative resulted in a standards-based methodology for population health queries, a reference implementation, and revision of the HQMF standard. It also informed future directions regarding interoperability and data access for ONC's Data Access Framework initiative. Conclusions: Query Health was a test of the learning health system that supplied a functional methodology and reference implementation for distributed population health queries that has been validated at three sites.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
039	<p>The Challenges of Implementing Next Generation Sequencing Across a Large Healthcare System, and the Molecular Epidemiology and Antibiotic Susceptibilities of Carbapenemase-Producing Bacteria in the Healthcare System of the U.S. Department of Defense</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27196272/</p>	<p>Objective: We sought to: 1) provide an overview of the genomic epidemiology of an extensive collection of carbapenemase-producing bacteria (CPB) collected in the U.S. Department of Defense health system; 2) increase awareness of the public availability of the sequences, isolates, and customized antimicrobial resistance database of that system; and 3) illustrate challenges and offer mitigations for implementing next generation sequencing (NGS) across large health systems. Design: Prospective surveillance and system-wide implementation of NGS. Setting: 288-hospital healthcare network. Methods: All phenotypically carbapenem resistant bacteria underwent CarbaNP® testing and PCR, followed by NGS. Commercial (Newbler and Geneious), on-line (ResFinder), and open-source software (Btrim, FLASH, Bowtie2, and Samtools) were used for assembly, SNP detection and clustering. Laboratory capacity, throughput, and response time were assessed. Results: From 2009 through 2015, 27,000 multidrug-resistant Gram-negative isolates were submitted. 225 contained carbapenemase-encoding genes (most commonly blaKPC, blaNDM, and blaOXA23). These were found in 15 species from 146 inpatients in 19 facilities. Genetically related CPB were found in more than one hospital. Other clusters or outbreaks were not clonal and involved genetically related plasmids, while some involved several unrelated plasmids. Relatedness depended on the clustering algorithm used. Transmission patterns of plasmids and other mobile genetic</p>	CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-abeerto.</p>

			<p>elements could not be determined without ultra-long read, single-molecule real-time sequencing. 80% of carbapenem-resistant phenotypes retained susceptibility to aminoglycosides, and 70% retained susceptibility to fluoroquinolones. However, among the CPB-confirmed genotypes, fewer than 25% retained susceptibility to aminoglycosides or fluoroquinolones. Conclusion: Although NGS is increasingly acclaimed to revolutionize clinical practice, resource-constrained environments, large or geographically dispersed healthcare networks, and military or government-funded public health laboratories are likely to encounter constraints and challenges as they implement NGS across their health systems. These include lack of standardized definitions and quality control metrics, limitations of short-read sequencing, insufficient bandwidth, and the current limited availability of very expensive and scarcely available sequencing platforms. Possible solutions and mitigations are also proposed.</p>			
040	<p>A biologically informed method for detecting rare variant associations</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27582876/</p>	<p>Background: BioBin is a bioinformatics software package developed to automate the process of binning rare variants into groups for statistical association analysis using a biological knowledge-driven framework. BioBin collapses variants into biological features such as genes, pathways, evolutionary conserved regions (ECRs), protein families, regulatory regions, and others based on user-designated parameters. BioBin provides the infrastructure to create complex and interesting hypotheses in an automated fashion thereby circumventing the necessity for advanced and time consuming scripting. Purpose of the study: In this manuscript, we describe the software package for BioBin, along with type I error and power simulations to demonstrate the strengths and various customizable features and analysis options of this variant binning tool. Results: Simulation testing highlights the utility of BioBin as a fast, comprehensive and expandable tool for the biologically-inspired binning and analysis of low-frequency variants in sequence data. Conclusions and potential implications: The BioBin software package has the capability to transform and streamline the analysis pipelines for researchers analyzing rare variants. This automated bioinformatics tool minimizes the manual effort of creating genomic regions for binning such that time can be spent on the much more interesting task of statistical analyses. This software package is open source and freely available from http://ritchielab.com/software/biobin-download</p>	CI1		
041	<p>The Collective Leadership for Safety Culture (Co-Lead) Team Intervention to Promote Teamwork and Patient Safety</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33266448/</p>	<p>Traditional hierarchical leadership has been implicated in patient safety failings internationally. Given that healthcare is almost wholly delivered by multidisciplinary teams, there have been calls for a more collective and team-based approach to the sharing of leadership and responsibility for patient safety. Although encouraging a collective approach to accountability can improve the provision of high quality and safe care, there is a lack of knowledge of how to train teams to adopt collective leadership. The Collective Leadership for Safety Cultures (Co-Lead) programme is a co-designed intervention for multidisciplinary healthcare teams. It is an open-source resource that offers teams a systematic approach to the development of collective leadership behaviours to promote effective teamworking and enhance patient safety cultures. This paper provides an overview of the co-design.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>

			<p>pilot testing, and refining of this novel intervention prior to its implementation and discusses key early findings from the evaluation. The Co-Lead intervention is grounded in the real-world experiences and identified needs and priorities of frontline healthcare staff and management and was co-designed based on the evidence for collective leadership and teamwork in healthcare. It has proven feasible to implement and effective in supporting teams to lead collectively to enhance safety culture. This intervention overview will be of value to healthcare teams and practitioners seeking to promote safety culture and effective teamworking by supporting teams to lead collectively.</p>			
042	<p>Improving predictive asthma algorithms with modelled environment data for Scotland: an observational cohort study protocol</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29780034/</p>	<p>Introduction: Asthma has a considerable, but potentially, avoidable burden on many populations globally. Scotland has some of the poorest health outcomes from asthma. Although ambient pollution, weather changes and sociodemographic factors have been associated with asthma attacks, it remains unclear whether modelled environment data and geospatial information can improve population-based asthma predictive algorithms. We aim to create the afferent loop of a national learning health system for asthma in Scotland. We will investigate the associations between ambient pollution, meteorological, geospatial and sociodemographic factors and asthma attacks. Methods and analysis: We will develop and implement a secured data governance and linkage framework to incorporate primary care health data, modelled environment data, geospatial population and sociodemographic data. Data from 75 recruited primary care practices (n=500 000 patients) in Scotland will be used. Modelled environment data on key air pollutants at a horizontal resolution of 5 km×5 km at hourly time steps will be generated using the EMEP4UK atmospheric chemistry transport modelling system for the datazones of the primary care practices' populations. Scottish population census and education databases will be incorporated into the linkage framework for analysis. We will then undertake a longitudinal retrospective observational analysis. Asthma outcomes include asthma hospitalisations and oral steroid prescriptions. Using a nested case-control study design, associations between all covariates will be measured using conditional logistic regression to account for the matched design and to identify suitable predictors and potential candidate algorithms for an asthma learning health system in Scotland. Findings from this study will contribute to the development of predictive algorithms for asthma outcomes and be used to form the basis for our learning health system prototype. Ethics and dissemination: The study received National Health Service Research Ethics Committee approval (16/SS/0130) and also obtained permissions via the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care in Scotland to access, collate and use the following data sets: population and housing census for Scotland; Scottish education data via the Scottish Exchange of Data and primary care data from general practice Data Custodians. Analytic code will be made available in the open source GitHub website. The results of this study will be published in international peer reviewed journals.</p>	CI1		
043	<p>Real-Time Dissemination</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32936691/</p>	<p>In the current era of patient empowerment and precision medicine, access to timely information is critical to decision-making. Unfortunately, we currently lack patient-specific, real-time data about clinical presentation, risk of thrombotic or hemorrhagic</p>	CI1		

	of Aggregate Data on Presentation and Outcomes of Patients With Venous Thromboembolism: The RIETE Infographics Project		events, key risk factors, and adverse outcomes in patients with venous thromboembolism (VTE). Accordingly, the Registro Informatizado Enfermedad TromboEmbólica (RIETE) investigators developed a tool to provide an open-source, real-time graphic representation of VTE-related data derived from over 90 000 patients with confirmed VTE. This information is intended to facilitate discussion in the informed decision-making process. The current article describes the aims, rationale, methods, and ongoing and future efforts of the real-time VTE infographics developed by the RIETE registry collaborators.			
044	Propagation of program control: a tool for distributed disease surveillance	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16621681/	<p>Purpose: The purpose of the study was (1) to identify the requirements for syndromic, disease surveillance and epidemiology systems arising from events such as the SARS outbreak in March 2003, and the deliberate spread of Bacillus anthracis, or anthrax, in the US in 2001; and (2) to use these specifications as input to the construction of a system intended to meet these requirements. An important goal was to provide information about the diffusion of a communicable disease without being dependent on centralised storage of information about individual patients or revealing patient-identifiable information.</p> <p>Methods: The method applied is rooted in the engineering paradigm involving phases of analysis, system specification, design, implementation, and testing. The requirements were established from earlier projects' conclusions and analysis of disease outbreaks. The requirements were validated by a literature study of syndromic and disease surveillance systems. The system was tested on simulated EHR databases generated from microbiology laboratory data.</p> <p>Results: A requirements list that a syndromic and disease surveillance system should meet, and an open source system, "The Snow Agent system", has been developed. The Snow Agent system is a distributed system for monitoring the status of a population's health by distributing processes to, and extracting epidemiological data directly from, the electronic health records (EHR) system in a geographic area.</p> <p>Conclusions: Syndromic and disease surveillance tools should be able to operate at all levels in the health systems and across national borders. Such systems should avoid transferring patient identifiable data, support two-way communications and be able to define and incorporate new and unknown diseases and syndrome definitions that should be reported by the system. The initial tests of the Snow Agent system shows that it will easily scale to national level in Norway.</p>	CII		
045	Predicting asthma attacks in primary care: protocol for developing a machine learning-based prediction model	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31292179/	<p>Introduction: Asthma is a long-term condition with rapid onset worsening of symptoms ('attacks') which can be unpredictable and may prove fatal. Models predicting asthma attacks require high sensitivity to minimise mortality risk, and high specificity to avoid unnecessary prescribing of preventative medications that carry an associated risk of adverse events. We aim to create a risk score to predict asthma attacks in primary care using a statistical learning approach trained on routinely collected electronic health record data.</p> <p>Methods and analysis: We will employ machine-learning classifiers (naïve Bayes, support vector machines, and random forests) to create an asthma attack risk prediction model, using the Asthma Learning Health System (ALHS) study patient registry comprising 500 000 individuals across 75 Scottish general</p>	CII		

			practices, with linked longitudinal primary care prescribing records, primary care Read codes, accident and emergency records, hospital admissions and deaths. Models will be compared on a partition of the dataset reserved for validation, and the final model will be tested in both an unseen partition of the derivation dataset and an external dataset from the Seasonal Influenza Vaccination Effectiveness II (SIVE II) study. Ethics and dissemination: Permissions for the ALHS project were obtained from the South East Scotland Research Ethics Committee 02 [16/SS/0130] and the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care (1516-0489). Permissions for the SIVE II project were obtained from the Privacy Advisory Committee (National Services NHS Scotland) [68/14] and the National Research Ethics Committee West Midlands-Edgbaston [15/WM/0035]. The subsequent research paper will be submitted for publication to a peer-reviewed journal and code scripts used for all components of the data cleaning, compiling, and analysis will be made available in the open source GitHub website (https://github.com/hollytibble).			
046	iGAS: A framework for using electronic intraoperative medical records for genomic discovery	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28193464/	Objective: Design and implement a HIPAA and Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (IHE) profile compliant automated pipeline, the integrated Genomics Anesthesia System (iGAS), linking genomic data from the Mount Sinai Health System (MSHS) BioMe biobank to electronic anesthesia records, including physiological data collected during the perioperative period. The resulting repository of multi-dimensional data can be used for precision medicine analysis of physiological readouts, acute medical conditions, and adverse events that can occur during surgery. Materials and methods: A structured pipeline was developed atop our existing anesthesia data warehouse using open-source tools. The pipeline is automated using scheduled tasks. The pipeline runs weekly, and finds and identifies all new and existing anesthetic records for BioMe participants. Results: The pipeline went live in June 2015 with 49.2% (n=15,673) of BioMe participants linked to 40,947 anesthetics. The pipeline runs weekly in minimal time. After eighteen months, an additional 3671 participants were enrolled in BioMe and the number of matched anesthetic records grew 21% to 49,545. Overall percentage of BioMe patients with anesthetics remained similar at 51.1% (n=18,128). Seven patients opted out during this time. The median number of anesthetics per participant was 2 (range 1-144). Collectively, there were over 35 million physiologic data points and 480,000 medication administrations linked to genomic data. To date, two projects are using the pipeline at MSHS. Conclusion: Automated integration of biobank and anesthetic data sources is feasible and practical. This integration enables large-scale genomic analyses that might inform variable physiological response to anesthetic and surgical stress, and examine genetic factors underlying adverse outcomes during and after surgery.	CII		
047	Civil-military cooperation in the early response to the COVID-19 pandemic in six	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33785587/	Background: The COVID-19 pandemic has presented many countries with significant health system and economic challenges. The role of civil-military cooperation in a health crisis of the magnitude presented by COVID-19 remains virtually unexplored. This review aims to detect and identify typologies, if any, of associations between security or military systems and the national response measures during the COVID-19, as adopted by six European countries during the early phase of the outbreak (January		CE5	Revisão da literatura.

	European countries		<p>to March 2020). Methods: We designed a structured qualitative literature review (qualitative evidence synthesis), primarily targeting open-source grey literature using a customised Google web search. Our target countries were UK, France, Spain, Italy, Belgium and Sweden. We employed a 'best fit' framework synthesis approach in qualitative analysis of the result records. Results: A total of 277 result records were included in our qualitative synthesis, with an overall search relevance yield of 46%. We identified 19 distinct descriptive categories of civil-military cooperation extending across seven analytical themes. Most prominent themes included how military support was incorporated in the national COVID-19 response, including support to national health systems, military repatriation and evacuation, and support to wider public systems. Conclusion: Findings of this review show the significance of military systems in supporting an expansive response during the COVID-19 pandemic, and our proposed methodological approach for capturing military health data in a reproducible manner and providing a comparative view on common types of interventions provided by civil-military cooperation to inform lessons from the use of military capacities during current COVID-19 outbreak.</p>			
048	Quality of routine facility data for monitoring priority maternal and newborn indicators in DHIS2: A case study from Gombe State, Nigeria	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30682130/	<p>Introduction: Routine health information systems are critical for monitoring service delivery. District Health Information System, version 2 (DHIS2) is an open source software platform used in more than 60 countries, on which global initiatives increasingly rely for such monitoring. We used facility-reported data in DHIS2 for Gombe State, north-eastern Nigeria, to present a case study of data quality to monitor priority maternal and neonatal health indicators. Methods: For all health facilities in DHIS2 offering antenatal and postnatal care services (n = 497) and labor and delivery services (n = 486), we assessed the quality of data for July 2016-June 2017 according to the World Health Organization data quality review guidance. Using data from DHIS2 as well as external facility-level and population-level household surveys, we reviewed three data quality dimensions-completeness and timeliness, internal consistency, and external consistency-and considered the opportunities for improvement. Results: Of 14 priority maternal and neonatal health indicators that could be tracked through facility-based data, 12 were included in Gombe's DHIS2. During July 2016-June 2017, facility-reported data in DHIS2 were incomplete at least 40% of the time, under-reported 10%-60% of the events documented in facility registers, and showed inconsistencies over time, between related indicators, and with an external data source. The best quality data elements were those that aligned with Gombe's health program priorities, particularly older health programs, and those that reflected contact indicators rather than indicators related to the provision of commodities or content of care. Conclusion: This case study from Gombe State, Nigeria, demonstrates the high potential for effective monitoring of maternal and neonatal health using DHIS2. However, coordinated action at multiple levels of the health system is needed to maximize reporting of existing data; rationalize data flow; routinize data quality review, feedback, and supervision; and ensure ongoing maintenance of DHIS2.</p>		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

049	<p>The Psychometric Properties of a Self-Administered, Open-Source Module for Valuing Metastatic Epidural Spinal Cord Compression Utilities</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30178420/</p>	<p>Introduction: Web surveys are often used for utility valuation. Typically, custom utility valuation tools that have not undergone psychometric evaluation are used. Objectives: This study aimed to determine the psychometric properties of a metastatic epidural spinal cord compression (MESCC) module run on a customizable open-source, internet-based, self-directed utility valuation platform (Self-directed Online Assessment of Preferences [SOAP]). Methods: Individuals accompanying patients to the emergency department waiting room in Ottawa, Canada, were recruited. Participants made SOAP MESCC health state valuations in the waiting room and 48 h later at home. Validity, agreement reliability, and responsiveness were measured by logical consistency of responses, smallest detectable change, the interclass correlation coefficient, and Guyatt's responsiveness index, respectively. Results: Of 285 participants who completed utility valuations, only 113 (39.6%) completed the re-test. Of these 113 participants, 92 (81.4%) provided valid responses on the first test and 75 (66.4%) provided valid responses on the test and re-test. Agreement for all groups of health states was adequate, since their smallest detectable change was less than the minimal clinically important difference. The mean interclass correlation coefficients for all health states were > 0.8, indicating at least substantial reliability. Guyatt's responsiveness indices all exceeded 0.80, indicating a high level of responsiveness. Conclusions: To our knowledge, this is the first validated open-source, web-based, self-directed utility valuation module. We have demonstrated the SOAP MESCC module is valid, reproducible, and responsive for obtaining ex ante utilities. Considering the successful psychometric validation of the SOAP MESCC module, other investigators can consider developing modules for other diseases where direct utility valuation is needed.</p>	CII	
050	<p>Mosquito habitat and dengue risk potential in Kenya: alternative methods to traditional risk mapping techniques</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25545930/</p>	<p>Outbreaks, epidemics and endemic conditions make dengue a disease that has emerged as a major threat in tropical and sub-tropical countries over the past 30 years. Dengue fever creates a growing burden for public health systems and has the potential to affect over 40% of the world population. The problem being investigated is to identify the highest and lowest areas of dengue risk. This paper presents "Similarity Search", a geospatial analysis aimed at identifying these locations within Kenya. Similarity Search develops a risk map by combining environmental susceptibility analysis and geographical information systems, and then compares areas with dengue prevalence to all other locations. Kenya has had outbreaks of dengue during the past 3 years, and we identified areas with the highest susceptibility to dengue infection using bioclimatic variables, elevation and mosquito habitat as input to the model. Comparison of the modelled risk map with the reported dengue epidemic cases obtained from the open source reporting ProMED and Government news reports from 1982-2013 confirmed the high-risk locations that were used as the Similarity Search presence cells. Developing the risk model based upon the bioclimatic variables, elevation and mosquito habitat increased the efficiency and effectiveness of the dengue fever risk mapping process.</p>	CII	
051	<p>Regenstrief Institute's</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24373714/</p>	<p>Objective: Regenstrief Institute developed one of the seminal computerized order entry systems, the Medical Gopher, for implementation at Wishard Hospital nearly three decades ago.</p>	CEI	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de</p>

	<p>Medical Gopher: a next-generation homegrown electronic medical record system</p>		<p>Wishard Hospital and Regenstrief remain committed to homegrown software development, and over the past 4 years we have fully rebuilt Gopher with an emphasis on usability, safety, leveraging open source technologies, and the advancement of biomedical informatics research. Our objective in this paper is to summarize the functionality of this new system and highlight its novel features. Materials and methods: Applying a user-centered design process, the new Gopher was built upon a rich-internet application framework using an agile development process. The system incorporates order entry, clinical documentation, result viewing, decision support, and clinical workflow. We have customized its use for the outpatient, inpatient, and emergency department settings. Results: The new Gopher is now in use by over 1100 users a day, including an average of 433 physicians caring for over 3600 patients daily. The system includes a wizard-like clinical workflow, dynamic multimedia alerts, and a familiar 'e-commerce'-based interface for order entry. Clinical documentation is enhanced by real-time natural language processing and data review is supported by a rapid chart search feature. Discussion: As one of the few remaining academically developed order entry systems, the Gopher has been designed both to improve patient care and to support next-generation informatics research. It has achieved rapid adoption within our health system and suggests continued viability for homegrown systems in settings of close collaboration between developers and providers.</p>			<p>um sistema.</p>
052	<p>Role of OpenEHR as an open source solution for the regional modelling of patient data in obstetrics</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25900270/</p>	<p>This work investigates, whether openEHR with its reference model, archetypes and templates is suitable for the digital representation of demographic as well as clinical data. Moreover, it elaborates openEHR as a tool for modelling Hospital Information Systems on a regional level based on a national logical infrastructure. OpenEHR is a dual model approach developed for the modelling of Hospital Information Systems enabling semantic interoperability. A holistic solution to this represents the use of dual model based Electronic Healthcare Record systems. Modelling data in the field of obstetrics is a challenge, since different regions demand locally specific information for the process of treatment. Smaller health units in developing countries like Brazil or Malaysia, which until recently handled automatable processes like the storage of sensitive patient data in paper form, start organizational reconstruction processes. This archetype proof-of-concept investigation has tried out some elements of the openEHR methodology in cooperation with a health unit in Colombo, Brazil. Two legal forms provided by the Brazilian Ministry of Health have been analyzed and classified into demographic and clinical data. LinkEHR-Ed editor was used to read, edit and create archetypes. Results show that 33 clinical and demographic concepts, which are necessary to cover data demanded by the Unified National Health System, were identified. Out of the concepts 61% were reused and 39% modified to cover domain requirements. The detailed process of reuse, modification and creation of archetypes is shown. We conclude that, although a major part of demographic and clinical patient data were already represented by existing archetypes, a significant part required major modifications. In this study openEHR proved to be a highly suitable tool in the modelling of complex health data. In combination with LinkEHR-Ed software it offers user-friendly and highly applicable tools, although the complexity built by the vast specifications requires expert networks to define generally excepted clinical models. Finally, this project has pointed out main</p>	<p>CI1</p>		

			benefits enclosing high coverage of obstetrics data on the Clinical Knowledge Manager, simple modelling, and wide network and support using openEHR. Moreover, barriers described are enclosing the allocation of clinical content to respective archetypes, as well as stagnant adaption of changes on the Clinical Knowledge Manager leading to redundant efforts in data contribution that need to be addressed in future works.			
053	Characterizing Chemical Terrorism Incidents Collected by the Global Terrorism Database, 1970-2015	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31280729/	<p>Background: The Global Terrorism Database (GTD) is an open-source database on terrorist incidents around the world since 1970, and it is maintained by the National Consortium for the Study of Terrorism and Responses to Terrorism (START; College Park, Maryland USA), a US Department of Homeland Security Center of Excellence. The consortium reviews media reports to determine if an event meets eligibility to be categorized as a terrorism incident for entry into the database. Objective: The objective of this study was to characterize chemical terrorism incidents reported to the GTD and understand more about the kinds of chemical agents used, the associated morbidity and mortality, the geography of incidents, and the intended targets. Methods: Chemical terrorism incidents from 1970 through 2015 were analyzed by chemical agent category, injury and fatality, geographic region, and target. Results: During the study period, 156,772 terrorism incidents were reported to the GTD, of which 292 (0.19%) met the inclusion criteria for analysis as a chemical terrorism incident. The reported chemical agent categories were: unknown chemical (30.5%); corrosives (23.3%); tear gas/mace (12.3%); unspecified gas (11.6%); cyanide (8.2%); pesticides (5.5%); metals (6.5%); and nerve gas (2.1%). On average, chemical terrorism incidents resulted in 51 injuries (mean range across agents: 2.5-1,622.0) and seven deaths (mean range across agents: 0.0-224.3) per incident. Nerve gas incidents (2.1%) had the highest mean number of injuries (n = 1,622) and fatalities (n = 224) per incident. The highest number of chemical terrorism incidents occurred in South Asia (29.5%), Western Europe (16.8%), and Middle East/North Africa (13.0%). The most common targets were private citizens (19.5%), of which groups of women (22.8%) were often the specific target. Incidents targeting educational institutions often specifically targeted female students or teachers (58.1%). Conclusions: Chemical terrorism incidents rarely occur; however, the use of certain chemical terrorism agents, for example nerve gas, can cause large mass-causality events that can kill or injure thousands with a single use. Certain regions of the world had higher frequency of chemical terrorism events overall, and also varied in their frequencies of the specific chemical terrorism agent used. Data suggest that morbidity and mortality vary by chemical category and by region. Results may be helpful in developing and optimizing regional chemical terrorism preparedness activities.</p>		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
054	OpenMRS as an emergency EMR-How we used a global good to create	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33752170/	<p>Background: As the coronavirus pandemic progressed through the United States, Indianapolis Emergency Medical Services (IEMS) identified a gap between the health system capacity and the projected need to support an overwhelmed health care system. In addressing emergencies or special cases, each medical institution in a metropolitan area typically has a siloed process for capturing emergency patient records. These approaches vary in technical capabilities and may include use of an electronic medical record</p>	CI1		

	<p>an emergency EMR in a week</p>		<p>system (EMR) or a hybrid paper/EMR process. Given the projected volume of patients for the COVID-19 pandemic and the proposed multi-institutional team approach needed in case of significant provider illness, IEMS sought a simple, efficient, consolidated EMR solution to support planning for the potential capacity gap. IEMS approached Regenstrief Institute (RI), an established partner with experience in supporting OpenMRS, a global good EMR platform that had been deployed in multiple settings globally. Objective: The purpose of this project was to determine if OpenMRS, a global good, could be used to quickly stand up a system that would meet the needs for health emergency data collection and reporting. Design and implementation methods: The team used an "all hands on deck" approach, bringing together technical and subject matter experts, and a human-centered and iterative process to ensure the system met the key needs of IEMS. The OpenMRS Reference Application was adapted to the specific need and deployed as Docker containers to servers within the Indiana Health Information Exchange. Project outcomes and lessons learned: In less than two weeks, the Regenstrief team was able to install, configure and set up a working version of OpenMRS to support the desired electronic record requirements for the IEMS disaster field clinics. Using a human-centered approach, the RI team developed, tested, and released a user-friendly, installation-ready solution complete with an end user manual and a base support plan. IEMS and RI are sharing this approach to demonstrate how a global good can quickly generate a solution for COVID-19 and other disaster responses. Conclusions: Open source global goods can rapidly be adapted to meet local needs in an emergency. OpenMRS can be adapted to meet the needs of basic emergency medical services registration, triage, and basic data collection.</p>			
055	<p>Satisfaction with Paper-Based Dental Records and Perception of Electronic Dental Records among Dental Professionals in Myanmar</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29181240/</p>	<p>Objectives: To overcome challenges in the implementation of electronic dental record systems in a low-resource setting, it is crucial to know the level of users' satisfaction with the existing system of paper-based dental records and their perceptions of electronic dental records. Methods: A cross-sectional paper-based questionnaire survey was conducted among Myanmar dental professionals who worked in one of two teaching hospitals or in private dental clinics. Descriptive data were analyzed and regression analysis was carried out to identify factors influencing perceptions of electronic dental records. Results: Most dental professionals (>60%) were satisfied with just three out of six aspects of paper-based dental records (familiarity, flexibility, and portability). In addition, generalized positive perceptions were found among decision makers towards electronic dental records, and 86% of dentists indicated that they were willing to use them. Financial concerns were identified as the most important barrier to the implementation of electronic dental records among dentists who were not willing to use the proposed system. Conclusions: The first step towards implementing electronic dental records in Myanmar should be improvement of the content and structure of paper-based dental records, especially in private dental clinics. Utilization of appropriate open-source electronic dental record software in private dental clinics is recommended to address perceived issues around financial barriers. For the long term, we recommend providing further education and training in health</p>		CES	Survey

			informatics to healthcare professionals to facilitate the efficient use of electronic dental record software in Myanmar in the future.			
056	Metabolomics Analytics Workflow for Epidemiological Research: Perspectives from the Consortium of Metabolomics Studies (COMETS)	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31319517/	The application of metabolomics technology to epidemiological studies is emerging as a new approach to elucidate disease etiology and for biomarker discovery. However, analysis of metabolomics data is complex and there is an urgent need for the standardization of analysis workflow and reporting of study findings. To inform the development of such guidelines, we conducted a survey of 47 cohort representatives from the Consortium of Metabolomics Studies (COMETS) to gain insights into the current strategies and procedures used for analyzing metabolomics data in epidemiological studies worldwide. The results indicated a variety of applied analytical strategies, from biospecimen and data pre-processing and quality control to statistical analysis and reporting of study findings. These strategies included methods commonly used within the metabolomics community and applied in epidemiological research, as well as novel approaches to pre-processing pipelines and data analysis. To help with these discrepancies, we propose use of open-source initiatives such as the online web-based tool COMETS Analytics, which includes helpful tools to guide analytical workflow and the standardized reporting of findings from metabolomics analyses within epidemiological studies. Ultimately, this will improve the quality of statistical analyses, research findings, and study reproducibility.		CE5	Survey.
057	Scalable Collaborative Infrastructure for a Learning Healthcare System (SCILHS): architecture	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24821734/	We describe the architecture of the Patient Centered Outcomes Research Institute (PCORI) funded Scalable Collaborative Infrastructure for a Learning Healthcare System (SCILHS, http://www.SCILHS.org) clinical data research network, which leverages the \$48 billion dollar federal investment in health information technology (IT) to enable a queryable semantic data model across 10 health systems covering more than 8 million patients, plugging universally into the point of care, generating evidence and discovery, and thereby enabling clinician and patient participation in research during the patient encounter. Central to the success of SCILHS is development of innovative 'apps' to improve PCOR research methods and capacitate point of care functions such as consent, enrollment, randomization, and outreach for patient-reported outcomes. SCILHS adapts and extends an existing national research network formed on an advanced IT infrastructure built with open source, free, modular components	CI1		
058	Comparison of Natural Language Processing Rules-based and Machine-learning Systems to Identify Lumbar Spine Imaging Findings Related to Low Back Pain	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29605561/	Rationale and objectives: To evaluate a natural language processing (NLP) system built with open-source tools for identification of lumbar spine imaging findings related to low back pain on magnetic resonance and x-ray radiology reports from four health systems. Materials and methods: We used a limited data set (de-identified except for dates) sampled from lumbar spine imaging reports of a prospectively assembled cohort of adults. From N = 178,333 reports, we randomly selected N = 871 to form a reference-standard dataset, consisting of N = 413 x-ray reports and N = 458 MR reports. Using standardized criteria, four spine experts annotated the presence of 26 findings, where 71 reports were annotated by all four experts and 800 were each annotated by two experts. We calculated inter-rater agreement and finding prevalence from annotated data. We randomly split the annotated data into development (80%) and testing (20%) sets. We developed an NLP system from both rule-based and machine-learned models. We validated the system using accuracy metrics such as sensitivity,		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta a avaliação do sistema.

			specificity, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC). Results: The multirater annotated dataset achieved inter-rater agreement of Cohen's kappa > 0.60 (substantial agreement) for 25 of 26 findings, with finding prevalence ranging from 3% to 89%. In the testing sample, rule-based and machine-learned predictions both had comparable average specificity (0.97 and 0.95, respectively). The machine-learned approach had a higher average sensitivity (0.94, compared to 0.83 for rules-based), and a higher overall AUC (0.98, compared to 0.90 for rules-based). Conclusions: Our NLP system performed well in identifying the 26 lumbar spine findings, as benchmarked by reference-standard annotation by medical experts. Machine-learned models provided substantial gains in model sensitivity with slight loss of specificity, and overall higher AUC.		
059	An open source tool to compute measures of inpatient glycemic control: translating from healthcare analytics research to clinical quality improvement	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34142017/	Objectives: The objective of this study is to facilitate monitoring of the quality of inpatient glycemic control by providing an open-source tool to compute glucometrics. To allay regulatory and privacy concerns, the tool is usable locally; no data are uploaded to the internet. Materials and methods: We extended code, initially developed for healthcare analytics research, to serve the clinical need for quality monitoring of diabetes. We built an application, with a graphical interface, which can be run locally without any internet connection. Results: We verified that our code produced results identical to prior work in glucometrics. We extended the prior work by including additional metrics and by providing user customizability. The software has been used at an academic healthcare institution. Conclusion: We successfully translated code used for research methods into an open source, user-friendly tool which hospitals may use to expedite quality measure computation for the management of inpatients with diabetes.	CI1	
060	Improving the performance of community health workers in humanitarian emergencies: a realist evaluation protocol for the PIECES programme	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27531730/	workers (CHWs) in humanitarian emergencies represents a key research gap within the field of human resources for health. This paper presents the research protocol for the Performance Improvement of CHWs in Emergency Settings (PIECES) research programme. Enhancing Learning and Research in Humanitarian Action (ELRHA) funded the development of this protocol as part of their Health in Humanitarian Crises (R2HC) call (No.19839). PIECES aims to understand what factors improve the performance of CHWs in level III humanitarian emergencies. Methods and analysis: The suggested protocol uses a realist evaluation with multiple cases across the 3 country sites: Turkey, Iraq and Lebanon. Working with International Medical Corps (IMC), an initial programme theory was elicited through literature and document reviews, semistructured interviews and focus groups with IMC programme managers and CHWs. Based on this initial theory, this protocol proposes a combination of semistructured interviews, life histories and critical incident narratives, surveys and latent variable modelling of key constructs to explain how contextual factors work to trigger mechanisms for specific outcomes relating to IMC's 300+ CHWs' performance. Participants will also include programme staff, CHWs and programme beneficiaries. Realist approaches will be used to better understand 'what works, for whom and under what conditions' for improving CHW performance within humanitarian contexts. Ethics and dissemination: Trinity College Dublin's Health Policy and Management/Centre for Global Health Research Ethics Committee	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			gave ethical approval for the protocol development phase. For the full research project, additional ethical approval will be sought from: Université St. Joseph (Lebanon), the Ethics Committee of the Ministry of Health in Baghdad (Iraq) and the Middle East Technical University (Turkey). Dissemination activities will involve a mixture of research feedback, policy briefs, guidelines and recommendations, as well as open source academic articles.			
061	A mobile system for the collection of clinical data and EEG signals by using the sana platform	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24851974/	Nowadays, more than 450 millions of people around the world suffer from mental disorders. One of the main problems of that type of illnesses is the lack of early detection, generally due to the reduced number of professionals specialized in mental health, especially in low- and middle-income countries. This article aims at describing the process of construction of an m-Health system that supports the collection of clinical data, including EEG signals, in order to assist the initial assessment of neurologic problems. The system has been mainly developed by using low-cost technology, implemented under the open-source platform SANA, and integrating a non-professional EEG device for the acquisition of bioelectric signals of the brain. The functionalities of this application and its usefulness have been evaluated by a group of six experts who concluded that a) the system implements 100% of the functionalities described in the system design phase, and b) the usefulness of the system's functionalities is 96%.	CI1		
062	One country's journey to interoperability: Tanzania's experience developing and implementing a national health information exchange	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33926428/	Background: Robust, flexible, and integrated health information (HIS) systems are essential to achieving national and international goals in health and development. Such systems are still uncommon in most low and middle income countries. This article describes a first-phase activity in Tanzania to integrate the country's vertical health management information system with the help of an interoperability layer that enables cross-program data exchange. Methods: From 2014 to 2019, the Tanzanian government and partners implemented a five-step procedure based on the "Mind the GAPS" (governance, architecture, program management, and standards) framework and using both proprietary and open-source tools. In collaboration with multiple stakeholders, the team developed the system to address major data challenges via four fully documented "use case scenarios" addressing data exchange among hospitals, between services and the supply chain, across digital data systems, and within the supply chain reporting system. This work included developing the architecture for health system data exchange, putting a middleware interoperability layer in place to facilitate the exchange, and training to support use of the system and the data it generates. Results: Tanzania successfully completed the five-step procedure for all four use cases. Data exchange is currently enabled among 15 separate information systems, and has resulted in improved data availability and significant time savings. The government has adopted the health information exchange within the national strategy for health care information, and the system is being operated and managed by Tanzanian officials. Conclusion: Developing an integrated HIS requires a significant time investment; but ultimately benefit both programs and patients. Tanzania's experience may interest countries that are developing their HIS programs.	CI1		

063	An innovative use of instant messaging technology to support a library's single-service point	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22559176/	A library service model that provides reference and instructional services by summoning reference librarians from a single service point is described. The system utilizes Libraryh3lp, an open-source, multioperator instant messaging system. The selection and refinement of this solution and technical challenges encountered are explored, as is the design of public services around this technology, usage of the system, and best practices. This service model, while a major cultural and procedural change at first, is now a routine aspect of customer service for this library.	CI1		
064	Void spot assay procedural optimization and software for rapid and objective quantification of rodent voiding function, including overlapping urine spots	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29972322/	Mouse urinary behavior is quantifiable and is used to pinpoint mechanisms of voiding dysfunction and evaluate potential human therapies. Approaches to evaluate mouse urinary function vary widely among laboratories, however, complicating cross-study comparisons. Here, we describe development and multi-institutional validation of a new tool for objective, consistent, and rapid analysis of mouse void spot assay (VSA) data. Void Whizzard is a freely available software plugin for FIJI (a distribution of ImageJ) that facilitates VSA image batch processing and data extraction. We describe its features, demonstrate them by evaluating how specific VSA method parameters influence voiding behavior, and establish Void Whizzard as an expedited method for VSA analysis. This study includes control and obese diabetic mice as models of urinary dysfunction to increase rigor and ensure relevance across distinct voiding patterns. In particular, we show that Void Whizzard is an effective tool for quantifying nonconcentric overlapping void spots, which commonly confound analyses. We also show that mouse genetics are consistently more influential than assay design parameters when it comes to VSA outcomes. None of the following procedural modifications to reduce overlapping spots masked these genetic-related differences: reduction of VSA testing duration, water access during the assay period, placement of a wire mesh cage bottom on top of or elevated over the filter paper, treatment of mesh with a hydrophobic spray, and size of wire mesh opening. The Void Whizzard software and rigorous validation of VSA methodological parameters described here advance the goal of standardizing mouse urinary phenotyping for comprehensive urinary phenome analyses.	CI1		
065	Engaging older adults in the visualization of sensor data facilitated by an open platform for connected devices	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27002473/	Background: The use of smart home sensor systems is growing primarily due to the appeal of unobtrusively monitoring older adult health and wellness. However, integrating large-scale sensor systems within residential settings can be challenging when deployment takes place across multiple environments, requiring customization of applications, connection across various devices and effective visualization of complex longitudinal data. Objective: The objective of the study was to demonstrate the implementation of a smart home system using an open, extensible platform in a real-world setting and develop an application to visualize data real time. Methods: We deployed the open source Lab of Things platform in a house of 11 residents as a demonstration of feasibility over the course of 3 months. The system consisted of Aeon Labs Z-wave Door/Window sensors and an Aeon Labs Multi-sensor that collected data on motion, temperature, luminosity, and humidity. We applied a Rapid Iterative Testing and Evaluation approach towards designing a visualization interface engaging gerontological experts. We then conducted a survey with 19 older adult and caregiver stakeholders	CI1		

			to inform further design revisions. Results: Our initial visualization mockups consisted of a bar chart representing activity level over time. Family members felt comfortable using the application. Older adults however, indicated it would be difficult to learn to use the application, and had trouble identifying utility. A key for older adults was ensuring that the data collected could be utilized by their family members, physicians, or caregivers. Conclusions: The approach described in this work is generalizable towards future smart home deployments and can be a valuable guide for researchers to scale a study across multiple homes and connected devices, and to create personalized interfaces for end users.		
066	Patient-Reported Outcome Measures in Colorectal Surgery: Construction of Core Measures Using Open-Source Research Method	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33710930/	Purpose. The primary aim of the study was to review the existing literature about patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) in colorectal cancer and IBD. The secondary aim was to present a road map to develop a core outcome set via opinion gathering using social media. Method. This study is the first step of a three-step project aimed at constructing simple, applicable PROMs in colorectal surgery. This article was written in a collaborative manner with authors invited both through Twitter via the #OpenSourceResearch hashtag. The 5 most used PROMs were presented and discussed as slides/images on Twitter. Inputs from a wide spectrum of participants including researchers, surgeons, physicians, nurses, patients, and patients' organizations were collected and analyzed. The final draft was emailed to all contributors and 6 patients' representatives for proofreading and approval. Results. Five PROM sets were identified and discussed: EORTC QLQ-CR29, IBDQ short health questionnaire, EORTC QLQ-C30, ED-Q5-5L, and Short Form-36. There were 315 tweets posted by 50 tweeters with 1458 retweets. Awareness about PROMs was generally limited. The general psycho-physical well-being score (GPP) was suggested and discussed, and then a survey was conducted in which more than 2/3 of voters agreed that GPP covers the most important aspects in PROMs. Conclusion. Despite the limitations of this exploratory study, it offered a new method to conduct clinical research with opportunity to engage patients. The general psycho-physical well-being score suggested as simple, applicable PROMs to be eventually combined procedure-specific, disease-specific, or symptom-specific PROMs if needed.	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
067	Experimental Set Up of P300 Based Brain Computer Interface Using a Bioamplifier and BCI2000 System for Patients with Spinal Cord Injury	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26512264/	Objective: Brain computer interface (BCI) is one of the most promising technologies for helping people with neurological disorders. Most current BCI systems are relatively expensive and difficult to set up. Therefore, we developed a P300-based BCI system with a cheap bioamplifier and open source software. The purpose of this study was to describe the setup process of the system and preliminary experimental results. Methods: Ten spinal cord-injured patients were recruited. We used a sixteen-channel EEG(KT88-1016, Contec, China) and BCI2000 software (Wadsworth center, NY, USA). Subjects were asked to spell a 5-character word using the P300-based BCI system with 10 minutes of training. EEG data were acquired during the experiment. After subjects spelled the word for ten trials, the spelling accuracy and information transfer rate (ITR) were obtained in each patients. Results: All subjects performed the experiment without difficulty. The mean accuracy was 59.4±22.8%. The spelling accuracy reversely correlated with the age. Younger subjects spelled with higher accuracy than older	CI1	

			<p>subjects (p=0.018). However, sex, injury level, time since injury and ASIA scale were not correlated with the accuracy. The mean of ITR was 2.26±1.22 bit/min. Conclusion: This study showed that a BCI system can be set up inexpensively with a low-price bioamplifier and open-source software. The spelling accuracy was moderately achieved with our system. P300-based BCI is useful in young patients, but modification is necessary in old patients who have low ability of recognition and concentration.</p>			
068	<p>An affordable HIV-1 drug resistance monitoring method for resource limited settings</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24747156/</p>	<p>HIV-1 drug resistance has the potential to seriously compromise the effectiveness and impact of antiretroviral therapy (ART). As ART programs in sub-Saharan Africa continue to expand, individuals on ART should be closely monitored for the emergence of drug resistance. Surveillance of transmitted drug resistance to track transmission of viral strains already resistant to ART is also critical. Unfortunately, drug resistance testing is still not readily accessible in resource limited settings, because genotyping is expensive and requires sophisticated laboratory and data management infrastructure. An open access genotypic drug resistance monitoring method to manage individuals and assess transmitted drug resistance is described. The method uses free open source software for the interpretation of drug resistance patterns and the generation of individual patient reports. The genotyping protocol has an amplification rate of greater than 95% for plasma samples with a viral load >1,000 HIV-1 RNA copies/ml. The sensitivity decreases significantly for viral loads <1,000 HIV-1 RNA copies/ml. The method described here was validated against a method of HIV-1 drug resistance testing approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the Viroseq genotyping method. Limitations of the method described here include the fact that it is not automated and that it also failed to amplify the circulating recombinant form CRF02_AG from a validation panel of samples, although it amplified subtypes A and B from the same panel.</p>	<p>CI1</p>		
069	<p>Validating Performance of a Hospital Discharge Planning Decision Tool in Community Hospitals</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28777233/</p>	<p>Purpose of study: The Early Screen for Discharge Planning (ESDP) is a decision support tool developed in an urban academic medical center. High ESDP scores identify patients with nonroutine discharge plans who would benefit from early discharge planning intervention. We aimed to determine the predictive performance of the ESDP in a different practice setting. Primary practice setting: Rural regional community hospital. Methodology and sample: We designed a comparative, descriptive survey study and enrolled a convenience sample of 222 patients (identified at admission) who provided informed consent. Sample characteristics and ESDP scores were collected during enrollment. The Problems After Discharge Questionnaire, EuroQoL-5Dimensions quality-of-life measure, length of stay, and use of post-acute care services were recorded after discharge. We compared outcomes between patients with low and high ESDP scores. Results: More than half of the sample (51.8%) had a high ESDP score. Patients with high ESDP scores reported more problems after discharge (p = .02), reported lower quality of life (p < .001), had longer length of stays (p = .04), and used post-acute care services (p = .006) more than patients with low ESDP scores. The difference in the average percentage of unmet needs was not statistically significant (p = .12), but patients with high ESDP scores reported more unmet needs than patients with low ESDP scores. Implications for case management practice: The value of systematically proactive approaches to discharge planning is</p>		<p>CE5</p>	<p>Survey</p>

			increasingly recognized, but establishing the performance capacity of support tools is critical for optimizing benefit. These study findings support use of the ESDP in regional community hospitals, making it a useful, open-source decision support tool for various health care delivery systems			
070	Enabling the Next-Generation Radiology Report: Description of Two New System Standards	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28968194/	Currently, most radiology reports are highly variable and consist of unconstrained narrative text. This variability limits the ability to extract information from the report to guide clinical care, populate a data registry, or support quality improvement. This article introduces two newly available standards that pertain to radiology reports. Management of Radiology Reporting Templates (MRRT) is an integration profile that defines the format and exchange mechanisms for radiology report templates. Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine Part 20 defines how reports built using MRRT-based templates can be transmitted into an electronic health record (EHR). Together, these two standards enable new ways to improve report consistency and completeness, ensure proper clinical action, and improve the quality of patient care. Commercial and open-source developers are beginning to incorporate these standards into clinical systems. The authors use an example of a patient with an incidentally detected lung nodule to illustrate how these standards improve the exchange of information. The clinical scenario follows the use of the appropriate template through the completion of the radiology report, with the incidental finding structured and coded to enable automated follow-up in the EHR. ©RSNA, 2017.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta a descrição de dois padrões.
071	Putting Stakeholder Engagement at the Center of Health Economic Modeling for Health Technology Assessment in the United States	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33982198/	While evidence generated from health economic (HE) models is being used more commonly in health technology assessment (HTA) in the US, it is not consistently adopted by different stakeholder groups or across therapeutic areas. We hypothesize that actively engaging with multiple stakeholder groups throughout the model development process may result in models more widely considered by decision makers. To test this hypothesis, the Innovation and Value Initiative has launched a modeling effort to build an open-source HE model focusing on the disease state 'major depressive disorder'. A 20-member advisory group has been formed with representatives from patients, employers, clinicians, innovators, payers, and researchers to guide the model development process. While this effort is still in the early stages, the ongoing stakeholder engagement effort has yielded valuable insights that inform the model design. We have also identified several challenges to implementing this new approach. Our early findings suggest that the stakeholder engagement approach to HE model development has the potential to improve HTA in the US.	CI1		
072	Algorithmic Detection of Boolean Logic Errors in Clinical Decision Support Statements	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33694144/	Objective: Clinical decision support (CDS) can contribute to quality and safety. Prior work has shown that errors in CDS systems are common and can lead to unintended consequences. Many CDS systems use Boolean logic, which can be difficult for CDS analysts to specify accurately. We set out to determine the prevalence of certain types of Boolean logic errors in CDS statements. Methods: Nine health care organizations extracted Boolean logic statements from their Epic electronic health record (EHR). We developed an open-source software tool , which implemented the Espresso logic minimization algorithm, to identify three classes of logic errors. Results: Participating organizations submitted 260,698 logic statements, of which 44,890 were minimized by Espresso. We found errors in 209 of them. Every participating organization had at least two errors, and all	CI1		

			<p>organizations reported that they would act on the feedback. Discussion: An automated algorithm can readily detect specific categories of Boolean CDS logic errors. These errors represent a minority of CDS errors, but very likely require correction to avoid patient safety issues. This process found only a few errors at each site, but the problem appears to be widespread, affecting all participating organizations. Conclusion: Both CDS implementers and EHR vendors should consider implementing similar algorithms as part of the CDS authoring process to reduce the number of errors in their CDS interventions.</p>			
073	<p>Advanced medical imaging protocol workflow-a flexible electronic solution to optimize process efficiency, care quality and patient safety in the National VA Enterprise</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23288437/</p>	<p>Radiologists routinely make decisions with only limited information when assigning protocol instructions for the performance of advanced medical imaging examinations. Opportunity exists to simultaneously improve the safety, quality and efficiency of this workflow through the application of an electronic solution leveraging health system resources to provide concise, tailored information and decision support in real-time. Such a system has been developed using an open source, open standards design for use within the Veterans Health Administration. The Radiology Protocol Tool Recorder (RAPTOR) project identified key process attributes as well as inherent weaknesses of paper processes and electronic emulators of paper processes to guide the development of its optimized electronic solution. The design provides a kernel that can be expanded to create an integrated radiology environment. RAPTOR has implications relevant to the greater health care community, and serves as a case model for modernization of legacy government health information systems.</p>	<p>CI1</p>		
074	<p>Ten lessons learnt: scaling and transitioning one of the largest mobile health communication programmes in the world to a national government.</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34312151/</p>	<p>There has been exponential growth in the numbers of 'digital development' programmes seeking to leverage technology to solve systemic challenges. However, despite promising results and a shift from pilots to scale-ups, many have failed to realise their full potential. This paper reflects on lessons learnt from scaling and transitioning one of the largest mobile health programmes in the world to the Indian government. The complementary suite of services was designed by BBC Media Action to strengthen families' reproductive, maternal, neonatal and child health behaviours. Mobile Academy was a training course to refresh frontline health workers' (FLHWs) knowledge and improve their interpersonal communication skills. Mobile <i>Kunji</i> was a job aid to support FLHWs' interactions with families. <i>Kilkari</i> delivered weekly audio information to families' phones to reinforce FLHWs' counselling. As of April 2019, when Mobile Academy and <i>Kilkari</i> were transitioned to the government, 206 000 FLHWs had graduated and <i>Kilkari</i> had reached 10 million subscribers. Lessons learnt include the following: (1) private sector business models are challenging in low-resource settings; (2) you may pilot 'apples' but scale 'oranges'; (3) trade-offs are required between ideal solution design and affordability; (4) programme components should be reassessed before scaling; (5) operational viability at scale is a prerequisite for sustainability; (6) consider the true cost of open-source software; (7) taking informed consent in low-resource settings is challenging; (8) big data offer promise, but social norms and SIM change constrain use; (9) successful government engagements require significant capacity; (10) define governance structures and roadmaps up front.</p>		<p>CE1</p>	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>

075	Chronic patient remote monitoring through the application of big data and internet of things	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34256646/	Chronic patients could benefit from the technological advances, but the clinical approaches for this kind of patients are still limited. This paper describes a system for chronic patients monitoring both, in home and external environments. For this purpose, we used novel technologies as big data, cloud computing and internet of things (IoT). Additionally, the system has been validated for three use cases: cardiovascular disease (CVD), hypertension (HPN) and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which were selected for their incidence in the population. This system is innovative within e-health, mainly due to the use of a big data architecture based on open-source components , also it provides a scalable and distributed environment for storage and processing of biomedical sensor data. The proposed system enables the incorporation of non-medical data sources in order to improve the self-management of chronic diseases and to develop better strategies for health interventions for chronic and dependents patients.	CII		
076	A rigorous algorithm to detect and clean inaccurate adult height records within EHR systems	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24734128/	Background: Height is a critical variable for many biomedical analyses because it is an important component of Body Mass Index (BMI). Transforming EHR height measures into meaningful research-ready values is challenging and there is limited information available on methods for "cleaning" these data. Objectives: We sought to develop an algorithm to clean adult height data extracted from EHR using only height values and associated ages. Results: The algorithm we developed is sensitive to normal decreases in adult height associated with aging, is implemented using an open-source software tool and is thus easily modifiable, and is freely available . We checked the performance of our algorithm using data from the Northwestern biobank and a replication sample from the Marshfield Clinic biobank obtained through our participation in the eMERGE consortium. The algorithm identified 1262 erroneous values from a total of 33937 records in the Northwestern sample. Replacing erroneous height values with those identified as correct by the algorithm resulted in meaningful changes in height and BMI records; median change in recorded height after cleaning was 7.6 cm and median change in BMI was 2.9 kg/m(2). Comparison of cleaned EHR height values to observer measured values showed that 94.5% (95% C.I 93.8-% - 95.2%) of cleaned values were within 3.5 cm of observer measured values. Conclusions: Our freely available height algorithm cleans EHR height data with only height and age inputs. Use of this algorithm will benefit groups trying to perform research with height and BMI data extracted from EHR.	CII		
077	Automated digital TIL analysis (ADTA) adds prognostic value to standard assessment of depth and ulceration in	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33531581/	Accurate prognostic biomarkers in early-stage melanoma are urgently needed to stratify patients for clinical trials of adjuvant therapy. We applied a previously developed open source deep learning algorithm to detect tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) in hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) images of early-stage melanomas. We tested whether automated digital (TIL) analysis (ADTA) improved accuracy of prediction of disease specific survival (DSS) based on current pathology standards. ADTA was applied to a training cohort (n = 80) and a cutoff value was defined based on a Receiver Operating Curve. ADTA was then applied to a validation cohort (n = 145) and the previously determined cutoff value was used to stratify high and low risk patients, as demonstrated by Kaplan-Meier analysis (p ≤ 0.001). Multivariable Cox proportional hazards analysis was performed using ADTA, depth, and	CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.	

	primary melanoma		ulceration as co-variables and showed that ADTA contributed to DSS prediction (HR: 4.18, CI 1.51-11.58, p = 0.006). ADTA provides an effective and attainable assessment of TILs and should be further evaluated in larger studies for inclusion in staging algorithms.			
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